

Textile Engineering College, Zorargonj, Chattogram.
Under Affiliation Of

Bangladesh University of Textiles

**REPORT ON
INDUSTRIAL ATTACHMENT
Duration
(15th April 2019 to 15th June 2019)
With**

Submitted By:

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

At the commencement I express my solemn gratefulness to Almighty Who gave me strength and ability to complete the industrial training and this report. May your name be exalted, honored and glorified. Now a warm felicitation goes for me to acknowledge the people, who hold the desirability for encouraging, praising, assisting, as well as believing me on the task of textile manufacturing activities that I have worked through my internship period. I feel privileged to express my regards & gratitude to honorable Principal of CTEC ENGR. MD. Ismail Molla Sir for providing me the chance to complete my industrial attachment with FOUR H GROUP.

Special thanks to my supervising teacher, Engr. TARIQUL ISLAM to whom I am extremely indebted for his tremendous support and guidance throughout my training period, without whose help it would not have been possible to complete the training successfully.

I would also like to take the opportunity to express my sincerest gratitude to the management, administration and personnel of 4H GROUP for their kind assistance. Heartfelt thanks goes to Mr. A.M. Alamgir, General Manager, Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd., FOUR H GROUP for his permission and excellent co-operation during the period of our training. I would also like to thank Engr. Mr. Masudur Rahman (Factory Manager) and Engr. Md. Adnan Kazmi (Production Manager) for their sincere support. The generous support is greatly appreciated. I would also like to thank Production Officers, Senior Production Officer and Other Officials of Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd. for helping me to complete industrial training successfully. My gratitude also go to all the employees of Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd for their sincere co-operation, support and valuable advices above all, I would like to acknowledge our deep debt to all teachers of our college, particularly of Wet Processing Department for their kind inspiration and help, which remain as the backdrop of all my efforts.

Finally, I would like to acknowledge that I remain responsible for the inadequacies and errors, which doubtless remain in the following report.

Chapter 01

Introduction

Industrial attachment is the first step to the professional life of a student, especially on the technical side. It is an indispensable part of the study. Although our campus is equipped with good lab facilities, it is not always possible to demonstrate real industrial processes in the lab. Thus, two months industrial attachment program in a composite mill was arranged for us.

Textile education cannot be completed without industrial training because this industrial attachment program minimizes the gap between theoretical and practical knowledge and makes us accustomed to an industrial environment. We got an opportunity to complete two months-long industrial training in Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd., a sister concern of Four H Group, which is a 100% export-oriented composite knit dyeing industry. It has well-planned & equipped Knit dyeing-finishing units in addition to facilitating knitting and knitwear manufacturing.

The broad objective of the report is to learn about the overall activities of different departments in FOUR H GROUP. Even though academic knowledge is not perfect, practical knowledge is essential with it.

Objectives:

- ✓ To enlarge the dimension of knowledge regarding dyeing as well as others.
- ✓ To define and evaluate the performance of the dyeing Department as well as others.
- ✓ To observe the effectiveness of the dyeing Department as well as others.
- ✓ To get additional knowledge in different sections of the organization.
- ✓ To interchange opinions of the officials regarding their organization.
- ✓ To know the economic condition of Bangladesh through the 4H GROUP of Bangladesh.
- ✓ To identify the difference between theory (what we have learned from the text) and practice (what is happened).
- ✓ To compare the improvement of the present condition of the 4H GROUP with the previous years.
- ✓ To mention the problems that the 4H GROUP face in the process of production and delivery of garments and give some suggestions.
- ✓ To identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the 4H GROUP.

Chapter 02

Factory Profile

FOUR H DYEING & PRINTING LTD

A SISTER CONCERN OF FOUR H GROUP

Name of Factory : Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd.

Factory Location : Arkan Road, Kalarpool, Chapra,Patiya, Chattogram.

Year of Established : 1st October, 2009

Factory Space : 436968.99 sq/ft

Machineries : 296 Sets

Total Employee : 806 Nos.

Production Capacity /Month : Knitting -8,32,000 kgs. Dyeing & Finishing-7,80,000kgs. Printing-1,30,000 kgs.

Product Item : All Type of Knitted Fabrics Dyeing (Single Jersey, Lycra Single Jersey, 1X1 Rib,1X1 Lycra Rib, 2X2 Rib, 2X2 L/Rib, Thermal, P/Interlock,F/Terry,Lacoste, Pique)

Address : Four H Group, Corporate Head Office 778, D.T. Road, Askarabad, Doublemooring, Chattogram, Bangladesh

Contact Person : Mr. G.S. Jamil (Managing Director)
E-mail : jamil@fourhgroup.com
Mr. Md. Hassan (Director)
E-mail : hassan@fourhgroup.com
Mr. A.M. Alamgir (General Manager)
E-mail : alamgir@fourhgroup.com
Md. Shahidul Islam (AGM/ Plant In Charge)
E-mail : shahid@fourhgroup.com
Mr. Feroz Haider (AGM Merchandising)
E-mail : feroz@fourhgroup.com
Mr.Masudur Rahman (Factory Manager)
E-mail : masud_dyeing@fourhgroup.com
Mr. Adnan Kazmi (Production Manager)
E-mail : kazmi_dyeing@fourhgroup.com

Customer : PVH,TESCO International Ltd, C & A, H & M, NEXT, Lindex, Celio, Lob Laws, Li & Fung, Maiden Form, Max UAE, Wool Worth, Target Australia, M & S etc.

Factory Area : 4,36968.99 Sq/ft

CLIENTS OF FOUR H

H&M

TESCO

LI & FUNG

celio*

PRIMARK®

Etam

Walmart*

Sainsbury's

PRODUCTS

Details of Factory Area

SL.	Location	Area
1	Ground Floor (Building A, B & C)	32771.68 sq/ft
2	1 st floor (building A,B & C)	33396.68 sq/ft
3	2 st floor (building A,B& C)	46096.68 sq/ft
4	3 rd floor (building A,B &C)	46096.68 sq/ft
5	4 th floor (building A,B & C)	46096.68 sq/ft
6	5 th floor (building A,B & C)	46096.68 sq/ft
7	Dyeing Shed	47074.89 sq/ft
8	Printing Shed	39626.50 sq/ft
9	Utility Shed, ETP & Including Office	35792.39 sq/ft
10	Industrial Shed-1 (Temporary Chemical Store)	3515.94 sq/ft
11	Industrial Shed-2 (Dining/Wastage/Screen Wash)	7536.63 sq/ft
12	Industrial Shed-3 (Temporary WastageShed/Storage)	6736.41 sq/ft
13	Industrial Shed-4 (Washing Plant/Maintenance/Chemical Store)	2802.66 sq/ft
14	Industrial Shed-5 {Storage(Soda + Lubricant)}	1950.57 sq/ft
15	Industrial Shed-6 (Storage for Civil Equipment)	659.37 sq/ft
16	Sub Station Shed	771.71 sq/ft
17	Mosque	1459.92 sq/ft
18	Wash Room (Beside Print & Leftover)	241.24 sq/ft
19	Temporary Chemical Shed & Others	38245.68 sq/ft

SL.	Name of Department	Manpower		
		Management Staffs	Workers	Total
01	Accounts	4		4
02	Admin	16	41	57
03	Batch	3	23	26
04	Civil	1	4	5
05	CPD	0	0	0
06	Dyeing	13	78	91
07	Electrical	5	10	15
08	Finishing	8	94	102
09	Knitting	8	163	171
10	Lab	12	10	22
11	Loader	0	15	15
12	Mechanical	6	16	22
13	Merchandising	19	0	19
14	Printing	20	-	-
15	Quality	13	-	-
16	Store	22	-	-
17	Utility		25	25
Grand Total=		150	656	806

TOTOL FEMALE WORKERS	68
TOTAL MALES	588
FEMALE STAFFS	9
MALE STAFFS	141
GRAND TOTAL	806

PROCESS FLOW CHART

CHAPTER 3

YARN TESTING DEPARTMENT

INTRODUCTION:

Yarn is the first production of textile. Yarn is made from fibre. There are two types of fiber.

- 1.Natural fibre
- 2.Synthitic fibre

NATURAL FIBRE:

EX: COTTON
WOOL
JUTE

SYNTHETIC FIBRE:

EX: ACRYLIC
POLYESTER
POLYAMIDE

DESCRIPTION	COUNT	COLOR/SUPPLIER
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER	22/1	BCVC20
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER	22/1	BCVC20
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER	22/1	BCVC20
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER RAW YARN	24/1	GARG ACRYLIC
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER RAW YARN	28/1	GARG ACRYLIC
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER RAW YARN	32/1	GARG ACRYLIC
60%COTTON 40%POLYESTER RAW YARN	32/1	SHAMEEM COMPOSITE

DESCRIPTION	COUNT	COLOR/SUPPLIER
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	30/1	G.MELLANGE
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	30/1	NAVY MELLANGE
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	40/1	BCVC 20
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	40/1	BCVC 30
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	40/1	BCVC 50
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	40/1	G.MELLANGE
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	40/1	RAW
85%COTTON 15%VISCOSE	40/1	MELLANGE
60%COTTON 40/1POLYESTER	42/1	H3AL5190
100%COTTON COMB	24/1	RAW
100%COTTON COMB	26/1	RAW
100%COTTON COMB	30/1	GARF ACRYLIC, PATSPIN INDIA, PAHARTALI TEXTILE
100%COTTON COMB	34/1	GARF ACRYLIC, PATSPIN INDIA, PAHARTALI TEXTILE
100%COTTON CARDED	34/1	RAW
100%ORGANIC COTTON COMB	26/1	NAHAR
100%ORGANIC COTTON COMB	30/1	PRECOT MERIDIAN, SUPER SPINNING
100%ORGANIC COTTON COMB	32/1	SUPER SPINNING, NAHAR

YARN TEST:

Mainly this types of yarn testes are doing in Four H...

1. Yarn Count
2. Twist Per Inch (TPI)
3. Elongation
4. Hairiness
5. Appearance
6. CSP Strength
7. Uniformity

YARN TEST REPORT:

FOUR H DYEING & PRINTING LTD
 Pakistan, Faisal-Chungi
In-House Test Report

Test YARN Supplier SEOSTING Code 274 Color 5/100 Yarn Description 100% COMB SPUN Ref No 21078-09-03		Test Ref No FHS-18-004 Test Order 22 Test Lot 22318 Date 23-04-18 Other Name Yarn	
--	--	--	--

Yarn Test Report		
01. Yarn Count 20/2 (20/2) (20/2) (20/2) (20/2)	Finding Reports 21.42	Requirement 22.50
02. Twist Per Inch 12.5 (12.5) (12.5) (12.5) (12.5)	12.5 ✓	12.50
04. Appearance (ASTM 2255) 05. CSP 20/2 (20/2) (20/2) (20/2)	Medium A 2255	Low-Medium A 2500

Fabric Test Report (4 point system)		
06. Nepe 07. Stab 08. Undereye (Thin-Thin) 09. Dead Cotton 10. Yarn Contamination	Low High-15-50% White (20-00%) Medium Nil High-15-50% White (20%)	Nil Less than 100% Low Nil Less than 100%

FOUND COUNT LOW, TWIST OK, COUNT High in dark, Stab High in white. All values marginally acceptable.

Fail
 Mr. Ahsan
Checked & Prepared

Match

 Mr. Maria
Checked By

Pass
 Mr. Ahsan
Checked By

Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd

Ashkan Road, Kalarpool, Patiya

Chittagong

Phone : 01819837737

Email : lab_dyeing@fourhgroup.com

Test Report - CSP

MAG SpinSoft

Version 1.1

Dry : **79.00 °F** Wet : **69.00 °F** RH : **59.00 %** Test Date & Time : 13-Jan-09 1:51 am

Customer ID : 42 **Customer Name :**
 Test ID : **RF411** No. of Test : **5** Count Type : **30 Combed** Nom. Strength : **83.33** Shift : **A**
 Dept. : **Ring Frame** Lot / m/c No: **1** Sam. Length : **120 yard** Nom. CSP : **2499.9** Operator : **Symun**
 Group(s) : **1** Count Unit : **NeC** Nom. Count : **30** Str. Unit : **lbf**
 DCP : FCCP : F Zone Settg : Avg. Speed : Ring Traveller : Break draft :
 BDCP : M Zone Settg : B Zone Settg : Twist Constant : Total Draft : Draft Constant :

Group : 1		Frame No. : 1				
	1	2	3	4	5	
W	2.210	2.182	2.194	2.192	2.186	
Cnt	29.316	29.692	29.530	29.557	29.638	
Str	99.550	102.940	107.150	70.740	103.630	
CSP	2918	3056	3164	2091	3071	
RCP	2999	3141	3252	2149	3156	

	Average	Min.	Max.	CV %	SD	Q95(±)	Q99(±)
W	2.193						
Cnt	29.547	29.316	29.692	0.488	0.144	0.166	0.260
Str	96.802	70.740	107.150	15.306	14.817	17.036	26.717
CSP	2860.000	2091.000	3164.000	15.342	438.770	504.492	791.176
RCP	2939.400	2149.000	3252.000	15.343	450.988	518.540	813.206

RKM Value : 17.420 RH RKM Value : 17.886 RH Count: 29.278 RH Strength: 100.382

Control Chart - CSP

Nominal Chart - CSP

Comments :

Operated by,

Checked by,

Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd.

Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd

Araken Road, Kalarpool, Patiya

Chittagong

Phone : 01819837737

Email : lab_dyeing@fourhgroup.com

Test Report - Twist

MAG SpinSoft

Version 1.1

Dry : **79.00 °F** Wet : **69.00 °F** RH : **59.00 %** Test Date & Time : 13-Jan-09 2:27 am

Customer ID : 42 Customer Name :

Test ID : **RF308** No. of Test : **5** Nom. Count : **30** Spec. Len. : **20.0 inch** Shift : **A**
 Dept. : **Ring Frame** Lot / m/c No. : **sample** Nom. Twist : **19.72** Yarn Type : **Single** Operator : **Symun**
 Group(s) : **1** Count Type : **30 Combed** Pre Set Val. : **46.0** Direction : **Z**

Group : 1		Frame No. : 1				
TN	1	2	3	4	5	
TPI	17.670	16.200	16.100	16.870	16.550	
TPM	695.668	637.794	633.857	664.172	651.573	
	Average	Min.	Max.	CV %	SD	Q95(±) Q99(±)
TPI	16.678	16.100	17.670	3.792	0.632	0.727 1.140
TPM	656.613	633.857	695.668	3.792	24.899	28.628 44.897

Control Chart - TPI

Comments :

Operated by,

Checked by,

TN - Test No. TPI - Twist Per Inch TPM - Twist Per Metre

13-Jan-2009

Page 1 of 1

3:27 am

CHAPTER 4

KNITTING SECTION

KNITTING:

Knitting is the second most popular technique of fabric or garment formation by inter-looping one or one set of yarns. Continuous length of yarn is converted into vertically intermeshed loops either by hand or by machine. The most important parameter of a knitted fabric is loop length which can be varied during knitting by changing machine parameters, process parameters and yarn parameters. The other important parameters of a knitted fabric which are considered for assessing the quality of the fabric are courses per inch, wales per inch, stitch density, GSM and tightness factor.

Different types of yarns , needle sizes & stitch types may be used to achieve knitted fabrics with diverse properties.

Knitting Types:

Weft knitting: In weft knitted structure, a horizontal row of loops can be made by using one thread and the thread runs in horizontal direction.

Warp knitting: In a warp knitted structure, each loop in the horizontal direction is made from a different thread and the no. of thread used to product such a fabric is at least equal to the number of loops in horizontal row. The thread runs thoroughly in a vertical direction.

Weft knit

Warp knit

Classification of Knitting:

Knitting Structure:

Course:

1. The series of loops those are connected horizontally, continuously are called as course.
2. The horizontal row of loops that are made by adjacent needles in the same knitting cycle.

Wales:

1. The series of loops that immeshes vertically arc known as Wales.
2. Verticle column of loops that are made from same needle in successive knitting cycle.

Course

Wales

Knitted stitch:

The knitted stitch is the basic unit of intermeshing. It usually consists of three or more intermeshed needle loops. The length of yarn required to produce a complete knitted loop (needle loop and sinker loop) is known as stitch length or loop length.

Knitted STITCH

Difference between Weft Knitting & Warp Knitting:

Warp Knitting

Weft Knitting

The loops are produced to the length of fabric.	The loops are produced to the width of the fabric.
It is elastic to the length.	It is elastic to the width.
Elasticity of the warp knitted fabrics is less than weft knitting.	Elasticity of the weft knitted fabrics is higher than warp knitting.
Its shrinkage properties is less.	Its shrinkage properties is higher than warp knitted fabrics.
Here courses are needed for each pattern row.	Courses are equal to the pattern.
Yarns are supplied from beam.	Yarns are supplied from cone.
At least one yarn is required for each needle.	Any number of needle.
Creating fabric by this method is suitable to dry wash.	Hand wash is suitable for weft knitting.
Any design is done easily.	All types of design is complex.
It is specially suitable for producing coarse fabric.	It is suitable for producing thin fabric.

Flow Chart of Knitting Department.

Knitting order collect from merchandising Department

Yarn Received from Yarn Store

M/C Wise Yarn Allocation

Set knitting parameter

Sample for bulk

Start Bulk Production

Grey Fabric Inspection

Fabric delivery to fabric store

ORGANOGRAM OF KNITTING SECTION

LAYOUT OF KNIT SECTION

Machine Summary of Knitting Section in – FOUR H GROUP:

Classification of Knitting Section:

Knitting section is divided into two section-

1. Circular knitting section.
2. Fabric inspection section.

SL.	Name of Machine	Capacity	Brand	Origin	Qty/Set
01	Single Jersey knitting m/c (30 Dia, 28 Gauge)	230 kg	Smart	Taiwan	33
02	Rib knitting m/c (30 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Smart	Taiwan	11
03	Rib knitting m/c (36 Dia, 28 Gauge)	200 kg	Smart	Taiwan	8
04	Single Jersey knitting m/c (30 Dia, 28 Gauge)	260 kg	Zentex	Singapore	2
05	Rib knitting m/c (30 Dia, 20 Gauge)	200 kg	Zentex	Singapore	2
06	Interlock knitting m/c (30 Dia, 28 Gauge)	200 kg	Zentex	Singapore	1
07	Single Jersey knitting m/c (13 Dia, 28 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
08	Single Jersey knitting m/c (15 Dia, 28 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
09	Single Jersey knitting m/c (17 Dia, 28 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
10	Single Jersey knitting m/c (19 Dia, 28 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	2
11	Single Jersey knitting m/c (19 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	3
12	Single Jersey knitting m/c (21 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	2
13	Single Jersey knitting m/c (23 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
14	Single Jersey knitting m/c (25 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
15	Single Jersey knitting m/c (27 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
16	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (13 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
17	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (15 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
18	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (17 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
19	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (19 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
20	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (21 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1

20	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (21 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
21	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (23 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	2
22	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (24 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
23	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (25 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
24	Rib Jersey knitting m/c (27 Dia, 18 Gauge)	200 kg	Hantex	Taiwan	1
25	Single Jersey knitting m/c (21 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Pailung	Taiwan	7
26	Single Jersey knitting m/c (23 Dia, 24 Gauge)	220 kg	Pailung	Taiwan	6
27	Single Jersey knitting m/c (25 Dia, 24 Gauge)	240 kg	Pailung	Taiwan	3
28	Single Jersey knitting m/c (27 Dia, 24 Gauge)	260 kg	Pailung	Taiwan	1
29	Single Jersey knitting m/c (19 Dia, 24 Gauge)	200 kg	Pailung	Taiwan	4
30	Single Jersey knitting m/c (30 Dia, 28 Gauge)	400 kg	Fukuhara	Japan	6
31	Single Jersey knitting m/c (30 Dia, 30 Gauge)	350 kg	Myer & Cie	Germany	10
32	Interlock knitting m/c (30 Dia, 24 Gauge)	250 kg	Fukuhara	Japan	4
33	Rib knitting m/c (30 Dia, 18 Gauge)	250 kg	Myer & Cie	Germany	2
Total					126

PHOTOS OF KNITTING

Circular Knitting m/c. - 01

Circular Knitting m/c. -02

Different parts of knitting machine:

Creel: Creel is used to place the cone.

Feeder: Feeder is used to feed the yarn.

Cam: Cam are the device which convert the rottery machine drive into a suitable reciprocating action for the needles or other elements.

Sinker: Sinker is used for Loop formation, holding down, knocking over.

Needle: Needle is used for loop formation.

Tensioning device: Tensioning device is used to give proper tension to the yarn.

VDQ pulley: VDQ pulley is used to control the GSM by controlling the stitch length.

Guide: Guide is used to guide the yarn.

Sensor: Sensor is used to seen & the machine stops when any problem occurs.

Spreader: Spreader is used to spread the knitted fabric before take up roller.

Take up roller: Take up roller is used to take up the fabric

Fixation feeder: These types of feeder are used in Electrical Auto Striper Knitting Machine to feed the yarn at specific finger.

Rethom: These devise are used in Electrical Auto Striper Knitting machine.

RAW MATERIALS USE FOR KNITTING:

Type of yarn	Count
Cotton Yarn	24 ^s , 26 ^s , 28 ^s , 30 ^s , 34 ^s , 36 ^s , 40 ^s
Polyester Yarn	75D, 100D,150D
Spandex yarn	20D,40D,70D
Grey Melange (C-90% V-10%)	24 ^s , 26 ^s ,30 ^s ,34 ^s
PC (65%Polyester & 35% cotton)	42 ^s ,40 ^s ,24 ^s , 26 ^s , 28 ^s , 30 ^s
CVC	42 ^s ,40 ^s ,24 ^s , 26 ^s , 28 ^s , 30 ^s

Different Types of Yarn

Cotton Carded Yarn

A cotton yarn that has been carded but not combed. Carded yarns contain a wider range of fiber lengths and, as a result, are not as uniform or as strong as combed yarns. They are considerably cheaper and are used in medium and coarse counts.

Cotton combed yarn

A process where the shorter cotton fibers are discarded, making the yarn stronger and softer. The combing process removes the short fibers and any debris that may be in the fiber when it was in the field. A cleaner, more uniform and lustrous yarn results.

Cotton yarn that has been combed to remove short fibers and straighten or arrange longer fibers in parallel order resulting in a smooth yarn used in finer garments.

Slub yarn

Yarn that is spun intentionally to achieve an irregular shape, in terms of length and diameter.

Slub yarn refers to yarn that has been purposely spun with slubs (thicker sections along the yarn).

While it was once seen only as a defect, *slub yarn* is now intentionally created to give fabric more personality.

CVC

A blended yarn having more percentage of cotton as compared to that of polyester is called chief value cotton or CVC yarn. For example, Cotton: Polyester is 70:30 or 60:40.

Polyester

Polyester is a category of polymers that contain the esterfunctional group in their main chain. As a specific material, it most commonly refers to a type called polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

Polyesters include naturally occurring chemicals, such as in the cutin of plant cuticles, as well as synthetics through step-growth polymerization such as polybutyrate. Natural polyesters and a few synthetic ones are biodegradable, but most synthetic polyesters are not. This material is used very widely in clothing.

Lycra

Lycra is a man-made elastic fibre invented and produced only by DuPont . It is INVISTA's trademark for a synthetic fabric material with elastic properties of the sort known generically as "spandex". Lycra is commonly used in athletic or active clothing. Lycra is never used alone; it is always combined with another fiber (or fibers), natural or man-made. Fabrics enhanced with lycra retain the appearance of the majority fibre.

END PRODUCTS OF CIRCULAR KNITTING MACHINE:

1. Single Jersey :

- a) Plain S/J
- b) Lycra S/J
- c) Single Lacoste
- d) Double Lacoste
- e) Single Pique
- f) Double Pique
- g) Fleece
- h) Terry
- i) Lycra S/L
- j) Lycra D/L
- k) Lycra S/P
- l) Lycra D/P

2. Double jersey :

- a) Rib
- b) Interlock
- c) Waffle

DIFFERENT FABRIC GSM AND THEIR YARN COUNT:**1. S/J without lycra –**

FABRIC GSM	YARN COUNT
110-120	42 ^S -40 ^S
120-130	40 ^S -34 ^S
130-140	34 ^S -32 ^S
140-150	32 ^S -30 ^S
150-160	30 ^S -28 ^S
160-170	28 ^S -24 ^S
170-210	24 ^S -20 ^S

2. Rib without lycra -

FABRIC GSM	YARN COUNT
180-190	34 ^S -32 ^S
190-200	32 ^S -30 ^S
200-215	30 ^S -28 ^S
215-230	28 ^S -26 ^S
230-250	26 ^S -24 ^S
250-300	24 ^S -20 ^S

3. Interlock without lycra -

FABRIC GSM	YARN COUNT
200-220	42 ^S -40 ^S
220-230	40 ^S -36 ^S
230-250	34 ^S -30 ^S
250-300	30 ^S -24 ^S

4. Lacoste without lycra -

FABRIC	GSM	YARN COUNT
	180-190	30 ^S -28 ^S
	190-210	28 ^S -26 ^S
	210-230	26 ^S -24 ^S
	230-250	24 ^S -20 ^S

5. Lycra Rib(40D)-

FABRIC	GSM	YARN COUNT
	230-240	34 ^S -30 ^S
	240-250	34 ^S
	250-280	30 ^S -26 ^S
	280-300	26 ^S -24 ^S

6. Lycra S/J(40D)

FABRIC	GSM	YARN COUNT
	180-190	34 ^S
	190-210	32 ^S -30 ^S
	210-220	28 ^S
	220-240	28 ^S

PRODUCTION CALCULATION:

A. Production/day in kg at 100% efficiency

$$\boxed{?} \frac{RPM \times \text{No. of Feeder} \times \text{No. of Needle} \times SL(mm) \times 60 \times 24}{2.204 \times 25.4 \times 36 \times 840 \times \text{Yarn count}}$$

B. GSM = ——— ; Here, T= yarn count in tex

S= stitch density

L= stitch length in mm

C. Eff —————

FOR EXAMPLE

Machine no: 201

$$s \times f \times n \times l \times 60 \times 24$$

Calculated production =

$$= \frac{21.4 \times 84 \times 2120 \times 2.75 \times 60 \times 24}{25.4 \times 36 \times 840 \times 2.204 \times 28}$$

$$= 319 \text{ Kg /day}$$

Actual production = 301 kg /day

Here,

RPM, $s = 21.6$ Needle, $n = 2120T$ Feeders, $f = 84$ Stitch length, $l = 2.75\text{mm}$ Count, $Ne = 28$ **PRODUCTION PARAMETER:**

- Machine Diameter;
- Machine rpm (revolution per minute);
- No. of feeds or feeders in use;
- Machine Gauge;
- Count of yarn;
- Required time (M/C running time)
- Machine running efficiency.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN KNITTING PARAMETERS:

1. Stitch length increase then reduce the GSM & yarn count.
2. If stitch length increase then fabric width increase and WPI decrease.
3. If machine gauge increase then fabric width increase.
4. If yarn count increase (courser) then fabric width increase.
5. If shrinkage increases then fabric width decrease but GSM and WPI increase.
6. For finer gauge, finer count yarn should use.
7. Grey GSM should be less than finish GSM

CONSIDERABLE POINTS TO PRODUCE KNIT FABRICS:

When a buyer orders for fabric then they mention some points related to production and quality. Before production of knitted fabric, these factors are needed to consider. Those are as follows-

1. Type of Fabric or design of Fabric.
2. Finished G.S.M.
3. Yarn count
4. Types of yarn (combed or carded)
5. Diameter of the fabric.
6. Stitch length
7. Color depth.

G.S.M. :

It is technical term that indicates the weight of the fabric per square meter.

Point considered while setting grey GSM:

Enzyme level

Color

Suited or non- suited

Changing of GSM:

Major control by VDQ pulley.

Minor control by stitch length adjustment.

Altering the position of the tension pulley changes the G.S.M. of the fabric. If pulley moves towards the positive directive then the G.S.M. is decrease. And in the reverse direction G.S.M will increase.

FACTORS THAT SHOULD BE CHANGED IN CASE OF FABRIC DESIGN ON:

Cam setting

Set of needle

Size of loop shape

EFFECT OF STITCH LENGTH ON COLOR DEPTH:

If the depth of color of the fabric is high loop length should be higher because in case of fabric with higher loop length is less compact. In dark shade dye take up% is high so GSM is adjusted then. Similarly in case of light shade loop length should be relatively smaller.

METHODS OF INCREASING PRODUCTION:

By the following methods the production of knitted fabric can be increased –

1. By increasing m/c speed:

Higher the m/c speed faster the movement of needle and ultimately production will be increased. But it has to make sure that excess tension is not imposed on yarn because of this high speed.

2. By increasing the number of feeder:

If the number of feeder is increased in the circumference of cylinder, then the number of courses will be increased in one revolution at a time.

3. By using machine of higher gauge:

The more the machine gauge, the more the production is. So by using machine of higher gauge production can be increased

4. By imposing automation in the m/c:

- a) Quick starting & stopping for efficient driving system.
- b) Automatic m/c lubrication system for smoother operation.
- c) PHoto electric fabric fault detector.

5. By imposing other developments:

Using creel-feeding system.

Applying yarn supply through plastic tube that eliminates the possibilities of yarn damage.

Quality control in knitting section

Every department of textile industry (spinning, dyeing, fabric, garments) should maintain their product quality. The proper operation of each department ensures a high quality product according to the buyer requirement. The Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd. is very conscious about their quality. In Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd. the knitting operation is supervised by knitting manager & production officer. They always observe, the workers either doing their work perfectly or not, such observation ultimately good quality product to the buyer.

List of equipment used in inspection-

- a. Inspection m/c
- b. Electronic balance
- c. GSM cutter

Inspection procedure-

As the fabric is produced by the circular knitting m/c, it is then collected by the quality inspector & the fabric is thoroughly inspected in front of a white light board. During this inspection the holes, oil marks, needle marks, sinker marks, barre effects etc are checked. If the fabric is within the acceptable level (by 4 point system) then it is sent to the batch section for dyeing or further treatment.

Quality Standard-

Four H dyeing & Printing Ltd. follows the 4 point grading system to inspect the body & rib of the fabric. In 4 point system the faults are found by inspection & are given points against the fault. Then the total no. of faults is calculated. The following table shows the 4 point system.

Defects size	Penalty points
0-3 inch	1
>3-6 inch	2
>6-9 inch	3
Above 9 inch	4
Hole < 1 inch	2
Hole > 1 inch	4

Quality Classification-

Penalty points	Grade
Upto 20	1 (A)
20-30	2 (B)
Above 30	3 (rejected)

Calculation of total points per yards:

In 4 point system fabric quality is evaluated by unit points/100 sq. yds

Points / 100 sq. yds = (Total points × 36 × 100) / (Fabric length in yds × Fabric width in inches)

Normally fabric roll containing below 28 points per 100 sq. yds are acceptable.

Knitted Fabric Faults:

Due to increasing the demand for quality knitted fabrics, high quality requirements are today greater since customer has become more aware of "Non-quality" problems, in order to avoid fabric rejection, knitting mills have to produce fabrics of high quality, constantly. Detection of faults during production of knitted fabric with circular knitting machine is crucial for improved quality and productivity. Any variation to the knitting process need to be investigated and corrected. The high quality standard can be guaranteed incorporating appropriate quality assurance. Industrial analysis indicate that quality can be improved, and defect cost minimized, by monitoring of the circular knitting process.

Sources of fabric faults:

1. Faults in yarn & the yarn Packages.
2. Yarn feeding & yarn feed regulator.
3. Machine setting & pattern defects.
4. Machine maintenance.
5. Climatic condition in the knitting plant.
6. Proper setting of the fall of cloth

Fabric faults:

Knitted fabric faults are very different in nature and appearance and are often superimposed. The most common faults are-

1. Hole or crack, broken ends
2. Drop stitch or loop
3. Pin hole
4. Oil mark
5. Needle mark
6. Sinker mark
7. Fabric patta
8. Crease mark

Hole :

Oil Stain

Needle Mark :

Sinker Mark

Pin hole :

Fly Contamination:

Fabric Press Of :

Lycra out :

Slub :

CHAPTER 5

LAB SECTION

INTRODUCTION:

4H Group has an Independent laboratory as international quality products are always ensured. The lab is to ensure adequate production, best quality etc. Lab is the research center of dyeing. Here all the testing of the fabric is done. Lab deep is prepared in the lab. Then this lab deep is provided for sample dyeing. According to recipe suggested by the lab. After sampling the fabric is tested in the lab according to buyer requirement. If all the requirements are acceptable then bulk production will run.

LAB DEPARTMENT:

Lab consists of three section. They are as follows...

1. Chemical testing lab
2. Physical testing lab 1
3. Physical testing lab 2

MACHINERY OF TESTING LAB:
TESTING LAB CONTAINS SUCH MACHINERY

Lab Equipment

SL.	Name of Equipment	Brand	Model	Origin	Number
1	Lab Dying Machine	Fong's	SDM2-12-140	China	6
2	IR Lab Dying Machine	SDL Atlas	D400IR	UK	1
3	Color Matching Cabinet	Macbeth	Judge II	USA	1
4	Color Matching Cabinet	Verivide	CAC-60-5	UK	1
5	Rota wash colorfastness Tester	SDL Atlas	M228B	UK	1
6	AATCC Crock Meter	SDL Atlas	M238AA	UK	1
7	ICI Pilling Tester	SDL Atlas	M227A	UK	1
8	Tumble Dryer	SDL Atlas	TVR2	UK	1
9	Tumble Dryer	Electrolux	T4130	UK	1
10	Washing Machine	Electrolux	FOM 71 CLS	Sweden	1
11	Washing Machine	Electrolux	W455H	Sweden	1
12	Quick Wash Plus Fabric Tester	SDL Atlas	M222QM	UK	1
13	Incubator & Perspirometer	SDL Atlas	M231	UK	1
14	Digital pH Meter	Hanna Instrument	G202	Mauritius	1
15	Digital pH Meter	Lutron		Taiwan	1
16	Digital Hygrometer (PH-208)	Lutron	TH03	Taiwan	1
17	TDS Tester	Hanna Instrument		Mauritius	2
18	Hardness Test Kits	Hanna Instrument		Mauritius	1
19	Pick Counters				3
20	Grey Scales	SDL Atlas	G246A/B	UK	2

21	Digital Balance (0.001gm-200gm)	KERN (A&D)		Japan	1
22	Digital Balance (0.001gm-200gm)	SDL Atlas	G204	UK	1
23	Mini Dryer	Rapid	R-3	China	2
24	Martindale abrasion & Pilling Tester	SDL Atlas	M235	UK	1
25	Spectrophotometer	X-Rite	CE7000A	USA	1
26	Tensile Tester	SDL Atlas	H5KT	UK	1
27	Light Fastness Tester	SDL Atlas	M237-105S	UK	1
28	Auto Bursting Strength Tester	SDL Atlas	M229	UK	1
29	Yarn Examining Machine	SDL Atlas	Y221	UK	1
30	Electronic Yarn Count System M/C	SDL Atlas	Y006	UK	1
31	Wrap Reel Electronic Machine	SDL Atlas	Y219BM	UK	1
32	Twister Hand Operated Machine	SDL Atlas	Y220A	UK	1
33	Whirlpool Front Loading Home Laundry Tumble Dryer (AATCC)	SDL Atlas	M223/7	UK	1
34	Whirlpool Top Loading Home Laundry Washing M/C (AATCC)	SDL Atlas	M223/5	UK	1
35	Incubator & Perspirometer	James H Heal	HX30	UK	1
36	Motorized Crock meter	James H Heal	680	UK	01
37	Electronic Pipette	Ranin	EDP	USA	01
38	Electronic heater	Palson	ES601-D1	China	02
39	Lab shaker			Korea	1
40	Wet & Dry bulb hygrometer	Zeal		UK	2
41	Over lock sewing machine	Pegasus		China	2
42	Plain Sewing Machine	Brother		China	1
43	Vacuum Cleaner				1
44	GSM Cutter	James H Heal		UK	1
45	UV/Visible Spectrophotometer	Perkin Elmer	Lamda 25	USA	1
46	Thermo stated water bath	J.P Selecta	Precistern	Spain	1
47	Electronic Lea Strength tester	Mag	Y0255	India	1
48	Magnetic Stirrer				1
49	Lab Air conditioning	Stulz			1
50	Dehumidifier				1
	Total				61

AUTO-DISPENSER MACHINE :

Datacolor automated dispensing system dispenses a wide range of solutions for textile exhaust and continuous dyeing, textile printing, floor covering, pigment industries and more. Datacolor AUTOLAB® Laboratory Dispenser Series gives the speed, precision and flexibility to provide accurate and repeatable recipes.

SPECTOPHOTOMETER:

FUCNTION: suggest about the color combination .From that most suitable combination is taken for dyeing.

IR LAB DYEING MACHINE

15 pots

SDL

Use: To dye the fabric it uses. At a time 15 samples can be dyed.

LAB DYEING MACHINE

8 POTS

FONGS

NUMBER: 02

Use: To dye the fabric it uses. At a time 8 samples can be dyed.

LAB DYEING MACHINE

12 POTS

FONGS

NUMBER: 03

Use: To dye the fabric it uses. At a time 12 samples can be dyed.

MINI PADDER

It has two rollers whose can be adjusted by arrangement.

Use: Fabric is squeezed between those rollers.

CAUTION HOT SURFACE

Use: Here temp can be up and down which is to increase the temperature of water for hot wash.

Generally used temperature is 90-100°C

MINI DRYER/STENTER

Use: It is used to dry the sample fabric.

Generally used temperature is 140°C

Time: 40-60s (depending on GSM of the fabric)

TUMBLE DRYER

STANDARDS-AATCC

WHIRLPOOL

Use: To dry the fabric after washing it is used.

It is used for the buyer who follows AATCC method.

Specially American based country follows this method.

TUMBLE DRYER

STANDARDS: ISO

IVR2

Use: To dry the fabric after washing it is used.

It is used for the buyer who follows ISO method.

TUMBLE DRYER

STANDARDS: ISO

T4130

ELECTROLUX

Use: To dry the fabric after washing it is used.

It is used for the buyer who follows AATCC method.

QUICK WASH PLUS

STANDARDS: AATCC & ISO

SDL-ATLAS:M222QW

Use: To wash the fabric it is used.

It is used for the buyer who follows AATCC & ISO method.

COLOR FASTNESS TESTER

STANDARDS:AATCC&ISO

SDL-ATLAS:M22813

Use: It is used for color fastness measuring

It is used for the buyer who follows AATCC & ISO method.

WASHING MACHINE -04

STANDARDS:AATCC

WHIRLPOOL

Use: To wash the fabric it is used.

It is used for the buyer who follows AATCC method.

Chemical: 66gm/wash AATCC reference detergent

Temp:40°C

Time:40min

EX.MAIDEN FOEM-41C 38 MIN

WASHING MACHINE-02

Standards:ISO

W455h

Electrolux

Use: to wash the fabric it is used. It is used for the buyer who follows iso method.

H&M-60°C

WASHING MACHINE-01

Standards:ISO

Wascator fom 71 cls

Electrolux

Use: To wash the fabric it is used. It is used for the buyer who follows ISO method.

ISO-6330:5A-40°C

EX-CELIO,TESCO,NEXT

ISO-6330:2A-60°C

EX-C&A

PHISICAL TESTING LAB-01

SEWING MACHINE

Use: To sew the fabric which will use for various testing as like pilling it is used.

RUBBING FASTNESS TESTER

STANDARDS: ISO & AATCC

JAMES H HEAL: 680MD

Use: It is used for measuring rubbing fastness of the fabric.

It is used for both the buyers who follows ISO & AATCC method

In AATCC method fabric should cut 45 angle

In ISO method fabric should cut 90 angle

Then color changing and color staining is assessed by gray scale.

Grade:1-5

DIGITAL pH/TEMPERATURE METER

HANNA INSTRUMENT

Use: It is used for measuring ph(alkalinity or acidity) of the fabric.

19. INCBATOR-01 & 02

SDLI-ATLAS

Standards: AATCC & ISO

Perspiration test (acid & alkali)

CF to water

Phenolic yellowing test

CF to saliva

Use: 1.To measure color fastness to perspiration.

2.To measure color fastness to water.

3.To measure color fastness to phenolic yellowing.

4. To measure color fastness to saliva.

It is used for both the buyers who follows ISO & AATCC method

Temperature: 37+/-2°c (ISO)

38+/-2°c (AATCC)

Time: 4hrs

20. ICI PILLING TESTER

STANDARDS:ISO 13945-1

SDL-ATLAS:M227A/B

Use: It is used to grade pilling condition.

It is used for the buyers who follows ISO method

Grade: 1-5

Revolution: 14400

Time: 4hrs

21. MARTINDALE PILLING TESTER

STANDARDS:ISO 13945-1

SDL-ATLAS:M227A/B

Use: It is used to grade pilling condition.

It is used for the buyers who follows ISO method

Grade:1-5

Revolution:14400

Time:4hrs

22. CROCK METER

AATCC-M238AA

Use: It is used for measuring rubbing fastness of the fabric.

It is used for the buyer who follows AATCC method

PHYSICAL TESTING LAB -02

22. WRAP REEL ELECTEONIC

SDL-ATLAS

Use: To wrap the yarn for count measuring.

23. ELECTRONIC YARN COUNT SYSTEM

SDL-ATLAS

Use: To measure yarn count.

24. TENSILE TESTER

TINIUS OLSEN, H5KT

SDL-ATLAS

Use: To measure tensile strength of yarn.

25. BURSTING STRENGTH TESTER

STANDARDS: ASTM & ISO

SDL-ATLAS:M229

Use: To measure bursting strength of fabric.

26. LIGHT FASTNESS TESTER

XENOTEST 150S+

ATLAS,M237-1505

STANDARDS:ISO 105 B02,B04

Use: To measure light fastness of the fabric.

27. TWIST TESTER

SDL-ATLAS

Use: To measure TPI.

28. YARN EXAMINING MACHINE

SDL-ATLAS

29. FABRIC GROWTH &RECOVERY TESTER

TEST METHOD: ASTM D2594

30. COLOR MATCHING CABINET

VERIVIDE

Use: It is used to grade the color changing & color staining.

It is used also for shade matching.

31. COLOR ASSESSMENT CABINET

MACBETH-X-RITE

Use: It is used to grade the color changing & color staining.

It is used also for shade matching.

PILLING ASSESMENT VIEWER

SDL-ATLAS

Use: It is used for grading pill.

LAB DIP

DEFINITION :

Lab Dip Development means the sample which is dyed according to buyer's requirements (similar shade and so on). Depending on lab dip development sample dyeing and bulk production dyeing planning done.

OBJECTIVE OF LAB DIP

The main objectives in lab dip are as follows.

- To calculate the recipe for sample dyeing.
- To compare dyed sample with swatch by light Box .
- To calculate revise recipe for sample dyeing.
- Finally approved Lab Dip(Grade: A B C)

Lab Dip Procedure: Lab dip is a process by which buyers supplied swatch is matched with the varying dyes percentage in the laboratory with or without help of "DATA COLOR"

Lab dip plays an important role in shade matching & and detaching the characteristics of the dyes and chemicals are to be used in the large scale of production so this is an important task before bulk production.

Lab dip Prepare flow chart

Available Stock Solutions:

- Red – 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% (very common)
- Yellow – 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% (very common)
- Blue - 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% (very common).

SHADE %	STOCK SOLUTION %
0.0001-0.009	0.1
0.10-0.99	0.5
1-1.99	1
2-3.99	2
4 (or above)	4

Depth of shade:

Four H Dyeing & Printing Ltd. produces 0.005% to 5% shade for the goods.

Recipe Calculation:

In lab, Fabric weight 10 gm

$$\text{Dyes (gm)} = \frac{\text{Shade \%} \times \text{Weight of the fabric in gm}}{\text{Stock solution \%}}$$

$$\text{Salt (gm)} = \frac{\text{Required amount (g/l)} \times \text{Liquor ratio} \times \text{sample weight}}{1000}$$

$$\text{Auxiliaries \& chemicals (cc/ml)} = \frac{\text{Required amount (g/l)} \times \text{Liquor ratio} \times \text{sample weight}}{1000 \times \text{concentration (\%)} \text{ of stock solution}}$$

For Caustic soda (38 Be.)

$$\text{Required alkali solution in (cc/ml)} = \frac{\text{Required amount (\%)} \times \text{wt of substrate} \times \text{LR}}{\text{Conversion value from } \underline{\underline{\text{Be.}}} \text{ to g/l of alkali}}$$

PROCESS FLOW CHART FOR COTTON DYEING

Auxiliaries- Sequestering Agent (SERAQUEST NEO)- 0.5 g/L

Leveling Agent (ALBATEC DBC(60°C)/SERAGEL C-FTRH(80°C))-1.0 g/L

Glauber Salt (Shade % Wise)

Soda Ash (Shade % Wise)

Dyestuff (Color)

Step 1: Required Water + Color + Galuber Salt +Cotton Fabric;

L:R- 1:8

PROCESS FLOW CHART FOR POLYESTER DYEING

Auxiliaries- Levelling Agent (Univadin Top)- 2.0 g/L
Anti creasing Agent (Rubine-OS)-1.0 g/L
Anti foaming Agent(Cibaflow Jet)- 0.4g/L
Buffer-AB-45 to adjust pH 4.5 to 5
Dyestuff (Color); L:R- 1:10

CHAPTER 6

BATCH SECTION

Batching: Batching means separation of fabric according to specification, Dyeing machine capacity & availability, urgency of the order.

Two types of Batching: 1. Solid 2. Assorted

Batch contains body of garments as well as collar-cuffs according to the design.

$$\text{Batch Quantity} = \frac{\text{Total required quantity} \times \text{Dia Quantity}}{\text{Total quantity}}$$

$$\text{Batch Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total batch quantity} + \text{total parts}}{\text{Batch Quantity}}$$

Batch distribution: - Batch is distributed according to nozzle capacity.

- During distribution maximum equilibrium of different parts is taken to consideration.

- Lycra fabrics are slit-cut to heat-set. That's why before dyeing they need to re-sewing. This is done by 'Back-sewing' machine.

-Tubular fabrics are turned into there backside by turning machine.

List of machines in Batch Section:

Batch Section	Back sewing m/c Manufacture: MTG MECCANICA SNC Country Of Origin : Italy		04
	Turning m/c Brand Name: HSING CHENG Country Of Origin : Thailand No of motor: 02 Motor: 210 HP Power: 220 V Year of Manufacture : 2006	Model: HC-TFM-1500 mm	03
	DONGA KOREA	MODEL-DAAT-4200	02
	Tumble Dryer Rated Power-8.4 Kw 200 V- 50 Hz CHINA	Model-TD-400	01
	Plaiting m/c		02

CHAPTER 7

DYEING SECTION

Dyeing:

"The process of applying color to fiber stock, yarn or fabric is called dyeing."

In another word,Dyeing is the process of adding color to textile products like fibers, yarns

and fabrics.Dyeing is normally done in a special solution containing dyes and particular chemical material. After dyeing,dye molecules have uncut chemical bond with fiber molecules.

The temperature and time controlling are two key factors in dyeing. Knit fabrics dyeing in batch process is very common in Winch Dyeing m/c. In FOUR H dyeing & printing Ltd. we are quite well known that, actually Winch & Jet Dyeing m/c are used here for knit dyeing

Reactive dyes combine directly with the fiber, resulting in excellent colorfastness. The first ranges of reactive dyes for cellulose fibers were introduced in the mid-1950. Today, a wide variety is available.

CHEMICAL USED IN 4H DYEING & PRINTING

1. WETTING AGENT- NOF/STN
2. ANTICREASE- JET
3. STABILIZER- DKM
4. SEQUESTERING- NEO
5. ENZYME- COMBI
6. SOAPING- NZA,RD
7. FIXING- FRD,ALBAFIX,ECO,SUN
8. PEROXIDE KILLER-PC
9. LEVELLING- CFTR,DBN

Details of Dyeing Machines in FOUR H Dyeing

Picture of Dyeing m/c

Fong's Sample dyeing m/c

Fong's HTHP (Jumbo flow) winch dyeing m/c

Pic: Canlar dyeing m/c

MACHINE NUMBER & CAPACITY

SL.	CAPACITY (KG)	BRAND	MODEL	Origin
1	600	Fong's	HSJ-3T	China
2	400	Fong's	HSJ-2T	China
3	1200	Fong's	ECO-38-6T	China
4	1000	Canlar	S-16726/27	Turkey
5	1000	Canlar	S-16726/27	Turkey
6	600	Fong's	ECO-38-3T	China
7	600	Fong's	ECO-38-3T	China
8	400	Fong's	ECO-38-2T	China
9	400	Fong's	ECO-38-2T	China
10	200	Fong's	ECO-38-1T	China
11	200	Fong's	ECO-38-1T	China
12	60	Fong's	ALLFIT-60	China
13	60	Fong's	ALLFIT-60	China
14	60	Fong's	ALLFIT-60	China
15	10	Fong's	ALLFIT-10	China
16	10	Fong's	ALLFIT-10	China
17	10	Fong's	ALLFIT-10	China
18	30	Fong's	ALLFIT-30	China
19	30	Fong's	ALLFIT-30	China
20	30	Fong's	ALLFIT-30	China
21	1600	Fong's	ECO-38-8T	China

22	1200	Fong's	HSJ-6T	China
23	1200	Canlar	S-16734/25735	Turkey
24	1200	Canlar	S-16734/25735	Turkey
25	10	Fong's	ALLFIT-10	China
26	120	Fong's	ALLFIT-10	China
27	10	Fong's	ALLFIT-120	China
28	120	Fong's	ALLFIT-120	China
29	120	Fong's	ALLFIT-120	China
30	2000	Canlar	S-15518	Turkey
31	200	Canlar	S-16686	Turkey

Influencing Factors For Dyeing:

- The pH of the dye.
- The temperature of bath.
- The concentration of the electrolyte.
- The time of dyeing.
- The liquor ratio.
- Dyeing auxiliaries.

STANDARD PROCESS CHART OF DYEING

DYEING PROCESS: FOR BLACK SHADE

Recipe:

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1. WETTING AGENT – 1 g/L | 10. MEGAFIX BLACK SUPER MS-2G(REACTIVE DYES) – 4.68691% |
| 2. DETERGENT – 1 g/L | 11. GLAUBER SALT – 80 g/L |
| 3. SCOURING AGENT(ENZYME) – 0.80% | 12. SODA ASH – 5 g/L |
| 4. ANTIFOAMING AGENT – 0.05 g/L | 13. CAUSTIC SODA – 1.50 g/L |
| 5. CITRIC ACID – 0.20% | 14. GREEN ACID – 1.50 g/L |
| 6. LEVELLING AGENT – 1.50g/L | 15. SOAPING AGENT – 1 g/L |
| 7. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.60 g/L | 16. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L |
| 8. MEGAFIX TOPAZ MS-2Y(REACTIVE DYES) – 1.01816% | 17. GREEN ACID – 0.60 g/L |
| 9. MEGAFIX GARNET MS-3R(REACTIVE DYES) – 0.65484% | 18. FIXING AGENT – 1 g/L |
| | 19. L:R- 1:6 |

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

Fixing dosing(D.T=20 min,R.T=20 min,Temp.=40°C)

Sample Check

Over flow once times run for 10 min

If OK then unload

SYMBOL:

Temp.=TEMPERATURE

D.T=DOSE TIME

R.T=RUN TIME

DYEING PROCESS: FOR WHITE SHADE

Recipe:

- | | |
|------------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1. ANTICREASING AGENT – 1 g/L | 8. BRIGHTENING AGENT – 0.00361 g/L |
| 2. WETTING AGENT – 0.40 g/L | 9. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L |
| 3. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L | 10. CITRIC ACID – 1.30% |
| 4. ANTI FOAMING AGENT – 0.05 g/L | 11. ENZYME – 0.30%drogen peroxide |
| 5. STABLIZER – 0.60 g/L | 12. HYDROZEN PEROXIDES 50% – 4 g/L |
| 6. BRIGHTENING AGENT – 0.01008 g/L | 13. SOFTNER – 1 g/L |
| 7. CAUSTIC SODA – 3 g/L | 14. L:R – 1:5 |

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

SYMBOL:

Temp.=TEMPERATURE

D.T=DOSE TIME

R.T=RUN TIME

DYEING PROCESS: FOR LIGHT SHADE

Recipe:

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| 1. WETTING AGENT – 0.50 g/L | 13. LEVELING AGENT – 1 g/L |
| 2. ANTI CREASING AGENT – 1 g/L | 14. REMAZOL YELLOW RR – 0.0044% |
| 3. SEQUESTERING AGENT- 0.20 g/L | 15. REMAZOL RED RR – 0.00661% |
| 4. STABLIZER – 0.30 g/L | 16. REMAZOL BLUE RR – 0.00039% |
| 5. ANTIFOAMING AGENT – 0.05 g/L | 17. GLAUBER SALT – 15 g/L |
| 6. CAUSTIC SODA – 1 g/L | 18. SODA ASH – 5 g/L |
| 7. SODA ASH – 2 g/L | 19. GREEN ACID – 0.80 g/L |
| 8. HYDROZEN PEROXIDE50% - 2 g/L | 20. SOAPING AGENT – 0.50 g/L |
| 9. PEROXIDE KILLER – 0.30 g/L | 21. FIXING AGENT – 0.50 g/L |
| 10. GREEN ACID – 0.80 g/L | 22. GREEN ACID – 0.60 g/L |
| 11. ENZYME – 0.20% | 23. ANTI YELLOWING AGENT – 0.50 g/L |
| 12. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L | 24. L:R – 1:8 |

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

DYEING PROCESS: FOR MEDIUM SHADE

Recipe:

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1. ANTICREASING AGENT – 1 g/L | 13. LEVELING AGENT – 1.50 g/L |
| 2. WETTING AGENT – 1 g/L | 14. NOVACRON YELLOW S-3R –0.00015% |
| 3. ANTIFOAMING AGENT –0.05 g/L | 15. NOVACRON RUBY S-3B – 0.04% |
| 4. STABLIZER – 0.30 g/L | 16. NOVA OCEAN S-R –0.60% |
| 5. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L | 17. GLAUBER SALT – 40.20 g/L |
| 6. CAUSTIC SODA – 1 g/L | 18. SODA ASH – 10 g/L |
| 7. SODA ASH – 2 g/L | 19. ACITIC ACID – 1.50 g/L |
| 8. HYDROZEN PEROXIDE50% – 2 g/L | 20. SOAPING AGENT – 1.02 g/L |
| 9. PEROXIDE KILLER – 0.30 g/L | 21. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L |
| 10. ENZYME – 0.10% | 22. FIXING AGENT – 1 g/L |
| 11. ANTOFOAMING AGENT – 0.20 g/L | 23. ACITIC ACID – 0.50 g/L |
| 12. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.80 g/L | 24. L:R – 1:5 |

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

DYEING PROCESS: FOR DEEP SHADE

Recipe:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. WETTING AGENT – 0.50 g/L 2. DETERGENT – 1 g/L 3. SCOURING AGENT(ENZYME) – 0.80% 4. ANTIFOAMING AGENT – 0.05 g/L 5. CITRIC ACID – 0.20% 6. LEVELLING AGENT – 1.50g/L 7. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L 8. REMAZOL ULTRA YELLOW RGBN(REACTIVE DYES) – 0.01% 9. REMAZOL ULTRA RED RGB(REACTIVE DYES) – 3.56% | <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. REMAZOL NAVY RGB (REACTIVE DYES) – 0.84% 11. GLAUBER SALT – 70 g/L 12. SODA ASH – 17.50 g/L 13. CAUSTIC SODA – 1.50 g/L 14. GREEN ACID – 0.80 g/L 15. SOAPING AGENT – 1 g/L 16. ENZYME – 0.30% 17. GREEN ACID – 0.60 g/L 18. FIXING AGENT – 1 g/L 19. L:R- 1:8 |
|---|---|

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

STANDARD WASH PROCESS CHART OF MELANCE & YARN DYED CONTINUITY

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

DYEING PROCESS: FOR TURQUOISE

Recipe:

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|--|
| 1. WETTING AGENT – 1.00 g/L | 13. LEVELING AGENT – 1.50 g/L |
| 2. ANTI CREASING AGENT – 1 g/L | 14. REMAZOL Brill. YELLOW 3GL – 0.41795% |
| 3. SEQUESTERING AGENT- 0.20 g/L | 15. REMAZOL Brill. BLUE RSPL – 0.12075% |
| 4. STABLIZER – 0.50 g/L | 16. REMAZOL TURQUOISE BLUE G – 0.03255% |
| 5. ANTIFOAMING AGENT – 2.05 g/L | 17. GLAUBER SALT – 30 g/L |
| 6. CAUSTIC SODA – 1 g/L | 18. SODA ASH – 5 g/L |
| 7. SODA ASH – 2 g/L | 19. ACETIC ACID – 0.80 g/L |
| 8. HYDROZEN PEROXIDE50% - 2 g/L | 20. SOAPING AGENT – 0.50 g/L |
| 9. PEROXIDE KILLER – 0.30 g/L | 21. FIXING AGENT – 0.50 g/L |
| 10. ACETIC ACID – 0.80 g/L | 22. ACETIC ACID – 0.60 g/L |
| 11. ENZYME – 0.50% | 23. L:R – 1:10 |
| 12. SEQUESTERING AGENT – 0.20 g/L | |

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

Topping

Topping is the process by which unmatched shade are matched again by adding color for that first the fabric is washed with soaping agent at full temp for making the shade light for better absorbency.

Leveling, Sequestering, Anti-crease are added by dosing for 3 min and run for 5 min at 60°C temp.

Salt is added by dosing for 10 min and give run time for 10 min. then color is added for 20 min.

After 10min salt sample is checked and then soda is added by dosing for 25 min. After 10 min

color steam is started for 60 min. When color is matched then bd is done and then BD wash is

performed. Then depending on shade acid or hot is done. Then fixing is applied at 30°C actually at

40°C temp.then by softener and anti-crease application fabric is unloaded.

PARTIAL STRIPPING:

It is the process by which unlevel dye is removed partially from the fabric.

PARTIAL STRIPPING RECIPE:

CITRIC ACID→ 2g/L

WETTING AGENT →0.5g/L

SALT→20g/L

CAUSTIC→5g/L

ACID → Control pH

TEMP→ 95°C

TIME→45min

PROCESS:

At first by 2.00g/L citric acid fabric is washed for 15 min in normal condition then it is washed in 60 temp for 15 min. Then by checking absorbency stripping is started by adding wetting agent. Salt is added by dosing and run time is given for 10 min. then caustic is added by dosing and run time for 10 min at 60°C temp. then temp is increased upto 95°C and run for 45 min.

STRIPPING:

Stripping is the process by which unlevel dye are being withdrawn from the fabric.

STRIPPING RECIPE:

CITRIC ACID → 2g/L

WETTING AGENT → 0.5g/L

CAUSTIC → 4-5g/L

HYDROSE → 4-5g/L

TEMP → 95°C

TIME → 45min

ACID → 0.8g/L (Neutralization)

PROCESS:

At first by 2.00g/L citric acid fabric is washed for 15 min in normal condition then it is washed in 60°C temp for 15 min. Then by checking absorbency stripping is started by adding wetting agent And caustic by dosing at 60°C temp. By giving 10 min run time temp is increased upto 90°C at 80°C temp hydrose is added. Here process is continued for 45 min.

DYEING PROCESS: FOR STRIPPING

SEQUENCE OF OPERATION

Dyeing Faults:

Common knit fabric dyeing faults and their way of remedies are given below.

Crack, Rope & Crease Marks

Causes:

1. Poor opening of the fabric rope.
2. Shock cooling of synthetic material.
3. Incorrect process procedure.
4. Higher fabric speed.

Remedies :

1. Pre-Heat setting.
2. Lower rate rising and cooling the temperature.
3. Reducing the m/c load.
4. Higher liquor ratio.
5. Running at a slightly higher nozzle pressure.

Fabric Distortion and Increase in Width

Causes :

1. Too high material speed.
2. Low liquor ratio.

Remedies :

1. By decreasing both nozzle pressure & winch speed.
2. By using high liquor ratio.

Pilling

Causes:

1. Too high mechanical stress on the surface of the fabric.
2. Excess speed during processing.
3. Excess foam formation in the dye bath.

Remedies:

1. By using of a suitable chemical lubricant.
2. By using antifoaming agent.
3. By turn reversing the Fabric before dyeing.

Running Problem

A. Ballooning :

Causes: Seam joining with too densely sewn.

Remedies : By cutting a vertical slit of 10-15 cm in length for escaping the air.

B. Intensive Foaming

Causes : Pumping a mixture of air and water.

Remedies : By using antifoaming agent.

Uneven Dyeing

Causes :

1. Uneven pretreatment (uneven scouring , bleaching & mercerizing).
2. Uneven heat-setting in case of synthetic fibers.
3. Quick addition of dyes and chemicals.
4. Lack of control of dyeing machine.

Remedies:

1. By ensuring even pretreatment.
2. By ensuring even heat-setting in case of synthetic fibers.
3. By slow addition of dyes and chemicals.
4. Proper controlling of dyeing machine.

Shade variation (Batch to batch)

Batch to batch shade variation is common in exhaust dyeing which is not completely avoidable.

Even though, to ensure a consistent batch to batch production of shade the following matters should be controlled carefully-

1. Use standard dyes and chemicals.
2. Maintain the same liquor ratio
3. Follow the standard pretreatment procedure.
4. Maintain the same dyeing cycle.
5. Identical dyeing procedure should be followed for the same depth of the shade.
6. Make sure that the operators add the right bulk chemicals at the same time and temperature in the process.
7. The Ph, hardness and sodium carbonate content of supply water should check daily.

Dye Spot

Causes : Improper mixing of dyestuff in the solution, in right amount of water, at the temperature

Remedies : We should pass the dissolved dyestuff through a fine stainless steel mesh strainer

Patchy Dyeing

Causes :

1. Uneven heat in the machine.
2. Improper impregnation of dye liquor due to the low wetting property of the fabric.
3. Dye migration during intermediate dyeing.

Remedies :

1. By proper pretreatment.
2. By adding extra wetting agent.
3. Heat should be same throughout the dye liquor.

Specky Dyeing

Causes :

1. Excessive foam in the dye bath.
2. Fall of water droplets on fabric surface before or after dyeing.
3. In sufficient after treatment.

Remedies :

1. By using antifoaming agent.
2. Sufficient after treatment.
3. By using a good wetting agent in the dye bath.

Crease Mark

Causes :

1. Poor opening of the fabric rope.
2. Shock cooling of synthetic material.
3. If pump pressure & reel speed is not equal
4. Due to high speed m/c running.

Remedies :

1. Maintaining proper reel speed & pumps speed.
2. Lower rate rising and cooling the temperature.
3. Reducing the m/c load.
4. Higher liquor ratio.

Dye Spot

Causes :

1. Improper Dissolving of dye particle in bath.
2. Improper Dissolving of caustic soda particle in bath.

Remedies :

1. By proper dissolving of dyes & chemicals.
2. By passing the dissolved dyestuff through a fine stainless steel mesh strainer, so that the large un-dissolved particles are removed.

Softener Mark

Causes :

1. Improper mixing of the Softener.
2. Improper running time of the fabric during application of softener.
3. Entanglement of the fabric during application of softener.

Remedies :

1. Maintaining proper reel speed & pumps speed.
2. Proper Mixing of the softener before addition.
3. Prevent the entanglement of the fabric during application of softener.

CHAPTER 9

PRINTING SECTION

Introduction:

Textile printing involves the production of a predetermined coloured pattern on a fabric, usually with a definite repeat. It can be described as a localised form of dyeing, applying colorant to selected areas of the fabric to build up the design. Textile Printing, like Textile dyeing, is a process for applying color to a substrate. However, instead of coloring the whole substrate (cloth, carpet or yarn) as in dyeing, print color is applied only to defined areas to obtain the desired pattern. This involves different techniques and different machinery with respect to dyeing, but the physical and chemical processes that take place between the dye and the fiber are analogous to dyeing.

The Term Printing is used to signify the production various means, of colored patterns of designs on textile materials other than woven, embroidered or painted designs. It is probably the cheapest method of ornamenting textile materials and is very popular because of the beautiful effects produced by it. An important feature of printing is that it enables the printer to cover up your or fabric defects to for greater extent than what dyeing or finishing could do.

Now-a-days, in the field of textile the acceptability of printing is increasing day by day. Printing makes the fabrics more attractive and charming. For producing a design effect on the surface of the fabric, printing is more easy than weaving. Moreover, the printing process is less time consuming, less expensive and appealing look at. In the recent period in every sphere of textile the importance of printing is developing due to its demand to the commoners.

Printing is a branch of dyeing and is generally defined as localized dyeing is dyeing which is confined to certain Protein of the fabric that constitute the design In printing color is applied not in the form of solution but in the form of thick paste containing the dye in a concentrated form. Textile printing is one kind of localized dyeing that is dyes or pigments are applied locally or discontinuously to produce various design on the fabric with a motif or motives in one move colors.

History of Printing:

Printing is a technique for printing text, images or patterns used widely throughout East Asia and probably originated in china in antiquity as a method of printing on textile and later paper. As a method of printing on cloth the earliest surviving examples from china date to before 220. Textile printing was known to Europe via the Islamic world form about 12th untruly and widely used.

The Incas of Peru, Chile and the Aztecs of Mexico also practiced textile printing previous the Spanish invasion in 1519 but owing to the imperfect character of their records before discovered the art for themselves or in some way learned its principles from the Asiatic.

During the later half of the 17th century the French brought directly by sea, from their colories, on the east coast of India, samples of Indian blue and white resist prints and along with them particulars of the processes by which they had been produced ,which produced washable fabrics. Textile printing was introduced into England in 1676 by an French refugee who opened works in that year on the banks of Thames near Richmond. In Germany too. Textile

printing was in all probability well established before it spread to England for towards the end of the 17th century, the district of Augsburg was celebrated for its printing linens a reputation not likely to have been built up had the industry been introduced later than 1676. As early as the 1630s, the East India Company was bringing in printed and plain cotton for the English market. By the 1660s British printers and dyers were making their own printed cotton to sell at home, printing single colors on plain background, less colorful than the imported prints, but more to the taste of the British. Designs were also sent to India for their craftspeople to copy for export back to England. There were many dyehouses in England in the latter half of 17th century. From an artistic point of view most of the pioneer work in calico printing was done by the French and so rapid was their advance in this branch of the business that they soon came to be acknowledged as its leading exponents. Their styles of design and schemes of color were closely followed even deliberately copied by all other Europeans.

LAYOUT OF PRINTING SECTION

Flow chart of wet process for printing fabric

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE

Flow chart of Printing Section

Screen Printing

Introduction to Screen printing:

Textile Printing is the process of applying color to fabric in definite patterns of designs, In properly printed fabrics the color is bonded with the fiber , so as do visits washing and friction. Textile printing is related to dyeing but where as in dyeing proper the whole fabric in uniformly covered with one color in printing one or more color is applied to it in certain parts only and in sharply defined patterns.In Printing, wooden block stencils engraved plates; yeller or silk screens can be med to place colors on the fabric. Colorants used in printing contain dyes thickened to prevent the color from spreading by capillary attraction beyond the limits of the pattern or design.

Screen printing is a printing technique that uses a woven mesh to support an ink blocking stencil. The attached stencil form open areas of mesh that trap ink or other printing materials which can be pressed through the mesh as a sharp-edged image onto a substrate. A roller or squeegee is moved across the screen stencil forcing or pumping ink past the threads of the woven mesh in the open areas. Screen printing is also a stencil method of print making in which a design is imposed on a screen of silk or other fine mesh with blank areas coated with an impermeable substance, and ink is forced through the mesh onto the printing surface. It is also known as silk screen, serigraphy and serigraph printing.

There are various terms used for what is essentially the same technique. Traditionally the process was called screen printing or silk screen printing because silk was used in the process. Currently synthetic threads are commonly used. In the screen printing process. The most popular mesh in general use is made of polyester. There are special use mesh materials of nylon and stainless steel available to the screen printing.

History

Screen printing first appeared in a recognizable form in china during song dynasty (960-1276AD). Japan and other Asian countries adopted this method of printing and advanced craft using it in conjunction with block printing and hand applied paints.

Screen printing was largely introduced to western Europe from Asia sometime

Until silk mesh was more available for trade from east and a profitable outlet for the medium discovered. Screen printing was first patented in England by Samuel simon in 1907. It was originally used as a popular method to print expensive wall paper, printed on linen, silk and other fine fabrics. Western screen printers developed reclusive defensive and exclusionary business policies intended to keep secret their workshops knowledge and technique.

Mesh :-

Mesh consists of semi-permeable barrier made of connected strands of metal fiber of other flexible/ ductile material. Mesh is similar to web or net in that it has many attached or woven strands.A mesh is often defined as a loosely woven or knitted fabric that has a large number of closely spaced holes frequently used for modern sports jerseys and other clothing.

Screen:-

A Screen is made of a piece of porous, finely woven fabric called mesh stretched over a frame of aluminum or wood. Originally human hair was used then silk was woven to make a screen mesh. Currently most mesh is woven of man-made materials such as steels nylon and non-permeable material to form a stencil, which is a negative of the image to be printed, that is the open spaces are where the ink will appear. Before ink is applied to the screen the screen and frame must go through a process referred to as pre press. In this process, an emulsion is scooped across the mesh and the exposure unit burns an area in the mesh with the identical shape as the desired image. The surface (commonly referred to as a pallet) that the substrate will be printed against is coated with a wide pallet tape. This serves to protect the pallet from any unwanted ink leaking through the substance and potentially staining the pallet or transferring unwanted ink onto the next substrate.

Some styles of printing:-

Style of printing refers to the printing of fabric with dyestuffs and related chemicals. In this case machineries are not readily related. There are different styles of printing. Among them following are important: -

1. Direct style
2. Dyed style
3. Resist or reserve style
4. Discharge style
5. Burn out style
6. Metal printing style
7. Azo color style
8. Crepon style
9. Flock style

CHEMICALS USED FOR PRINTING

SL NO.	Name of goods	Function of Dyes Chemicals	Remarks
Dyes(Pigment):			
1	Bezaprint Yellow RR	Pigment Dyes	CHT-BEZEMA
2	Bezaprint Yellow 3-GT	Pigment Dyes	
3	Bezaprint Orange RG	Pigment Dyes	
4	Bezaprint Violet KB	Pigment Dyes	
5	Bezaprint Grey-BB	Pigment Dyes	
6	Bezaprint Green BT	Pigment Dyes	
7	Bezaprint Violet FB	Pigment Dyes	
8	Bezaprint Brown RP	Pigment Dyes	
9	Bezaprint Red HBB	Pigment Dyes	
10	Bezaprint Red KGC	Pigment Dyes	
11	BezafLOUR Orange R	Fluorescent Dyes	
12	BezafLOUR Red R	Fluorescent Dyes	
13	BezafLOUR Violet BR-NF	Fluorescent Dyes	
14	BezafLOUR Orange RS-NF	Fluorescent Dyes	
15	BezafLOUR Yellow BS-NF	Fluorescent Dyes	
16	BezafLOUR Pink BS-NF	Fluorescent Dyes	
17	BezafLOUR Red RS-NF	Fluorescent Dyes	
18	Helizarin Lemon Yellow FF-G	Pigment Dyes	BASF
19	Printofix Red HB-K	Pigment Dyes	ARCHROMA
20	Printofix Orange H-R	Pigment Dyes	
21	Printofix Red T-N -01	Pigment Dyes	
22	Printofix Black T-M	Pigment Dyes	
23	Printofix Blue H-BP	Pigment Dyes	
24	Printofix Blue H-G	Pigment Dyes	
25	Printofix Green T-X	Pigment Dyes	
26	Printofix Turquoise Blue R-BD	Pigment Dyes	
27	Color Match PH-451 Green	Radiant Color	
Chemicals:			
28	Tubivis DRL-170	Additive	CHT-BEZEMA
29	Tubifast -4510 FF	Binder	
30	Tubifix P-70	Fixing Agent	
31	Tubisoft PS	Softener	
32	CHT-Entchimer BSN	Antifoam	
33	Tubiprint BL	Leveling Agent	
34	Tubigat - AR	Emulsifier	
35	Arristan 64	Softener	
36	Tubigat - R-130 New	Emulsifier	
37	Tubiscreen GD-200	Glitter Binder	
38	Asulak E-LY	Rubber Clear	ASUTEX
39	Asublance E-LY V	Rubber White	
40	Asulak E-T FE	Rubber Clear	
41	Asublance E-T FE	Rubber White	
42	Asulak E-961	Paste for Pigment print	
43	Printgum M-AP New	Adhesive	
44	Catalizador EPF	Crosslinking/Fixing Agent	
45	Lutexal Thickner HC	Thickner	BASF
46	Luprintol PE New	Emulsifier	
47	SP-1300 HV	Photo Emulsion	DYSIN
48	Hardener - A	Hardener	
49	Hardener - DL	Hardener	
50	Tex Agent-300	Clear	

SL NO.	Name of goods	Function of Dyes Chemicals	Remarks
51	Glycerne	Hygroscopic Agent	LOCAL
52	Amonia	Buffer	
53	PVA GUM	Additive	
54	Urea		
55	Carbolic Acid	Washing Chemicals	
56	Silver Glitter SG-00.15	Glitting	
57	Silver Metallic Powder	Glitting	
58	Golden Metallic Powder	Glitting	
59	Opel White		
60	Green Glitter		
61	Fortune Discharge CDW		
62	Fortune Discharge CDT		
63	Fortune Discharge Activator		
64	Multi Silver Glitter		
65	Titanium Di-oxide KA-100		
66	Golden Glitter		
67	Blue Glitter		
68	Golden Metallic Paste		
69	Asublance E-NT FF		
70	Octamine Yellow FT-GGP	Pigment Dyes	
71	Octamine Orange FT-2RG	Pigment Dyes	
72	Octamine Red FT-GR New	Pigment Dyes	
73	Forcolor Blue F2GL	Pigment Dyes	
74	Forcolor Black HFN	Pigment Dyes	
75	Forcolor Navy Blue FR	Pigment Dyes	
76	Forthick HV	Thickner	
77	For White SGL-100	Rubber	
78	For Clear SGL-200	Clear	

Order/ swatch collection:

Company's merchandiser will collect order from buyer and get swatch of ordered fabric or pantone number of different color used in the printing design. Orders are collected from the buyer regarding the capacity quantity, skillness and other important factors of the printing section. Clifton Group have a capacity to print out the design with maximum 9 colors. So any design beyond this limit cannot be processed in this section moreover they also accustomed to printing in cotton and cotton spender blend. So merchandiser should keep this factors under consideration during order collection.

Order analysis:

Swatch or order sheets get from the buyers analyzed with expert eyes of the factory. They define the color tone, hue, sharp line, outline and many other things of the ordered design. Sometime they take the help of color analysis machineries in this regard.

Design Scratch building:

With the help of special computer ordered design on the computer screen. Will then be divided according to their color separately with the action of software.

Screen preparation:

Screen may be defined as a piece of porous finely woven fabric called mesh stretched over a frame of aluminum or wood. The length of the design in the screen may be differed according to the requirement basically its length may be 60-62Inch and width in about 32-36Inch. At first this mesh screen is fully covered with photo emulsion name auto sol sp 1500 Hv. The special feature of this emulsion is to harden at the presence of light. Design of a single color outline or ground fabric scratched by computer is drawn over the screen separately with black reactive ink by the help of auto screening or auto exposing machine. Then this design is exposed to light of 3000 volt for few seconds according to the depth or complexity of design a generally about 40 seconds this screen is then washed with water. As a result, the unhardened emulsion covered with black ink is washed out and pigments are passed out through the pores of mesh and design is printing out.

Printing paste preparation:

Recipe for deep shade

1. Binder	– 140-180 g/L
2. Softener	– 15-30 g/L
3. Fixer	– 5 g/L
4. Antifoam	– 0.5 g/L
5. Liquor Ammonia	– 1-2 g/L (depending on pH 8-9)
6.D.R.L (Thickener)	– 20-30 g/L
7.Emulsifier	– 5 g/L

Recipe for a light shade

1. Binder	– 40-80 g/L
2. D.R.L. (thickener)	– 5%
3. Softener	– 10%
4. Fixer	– 5%
5. Liquor ammonia	– 1.0%
6. Emulsifier	– 3.0%

Preproduction :

Preproduction sample is made in order to check the whole process , recipe and procedure are buyer oriented or not. Preproduction sample must be get approval of buyer for bulk production. P.P sample is to be sent for buyer approval.

Comments Adjustment :

After getting the p. p sample buyer will comment or issue instruction for the correction of sample. The manufacturing company take necessary steps to overcome the faults occur in preproduction.

Bulk Production:

Then production for the whole bulk will start according to the buyer recommendation during the bulk production cares and correction are taken to overcome any kinds of printing faults.

Screen arrangement:

Screen must have to be arranged in a definite sequence. Generally its sequenced from deep to light color. That means screen must be arranged according to the deepness of color. But contrast color are not place one after another contrast color are those which produce third color in their mixing basically ground color and outlines screen is placed at first moreover experience of the executives will lead to the proper sequence of the screen. A lot of hard work and experience is required to make the proper arrangement of the screen.

Procedure of bulk production:

The fabric which is to be printed is at first loaded an the machine manually. The screens of different colors are arranged as they would not aerate any harm to the design printed. The number of screen will be as equal with the number of color in the screen. Moreover a screen for the outlines may also be used. Then the fabric is passed through a liqueur which acts as a blanket adhesive. In this company polyvinyl alcohol is used as a blanket adhesive. It is used in order to resist the spread out of the fabric during the screen design printing . then the fabric is passed but the blanket and consecutive screens. Pigment dyes paste is placed over the screen and a rubber/Auto squeezer is used to spread out the color uniformly over the mesh fabric As a result of the action of auto squeezer the design with the desired color is printed on the surface of the fabric. Then the fabric is carried out through a drier where the temp is 135-140 c Time for the daring is is about 3 min. then the fabric become hard as moisture removed by the dryer.

After that finishing process is performed. At this stage curing is carried out in a stenter machine. Here softener named Ariston 64 is used to remove the hardness of the fabric at a rate of 5+10gm per liter Ariston 64 is a silicon softer curing process is carried out generally at 150-155c for 5 min. But for the commercial purpose, the temp is increased to reduce the time. In this factory it is carried out at 170c for 1.5 min then the fabric is released form the machine and sent for impaction.

Basic faults Occurs during printing

- **Print bleeding**
- **Print missed**
- **Design out**
- **Dust**
- **Back impression**

Print bleeding: It occurs due to thickness of the printing paste. The outline of the design is spread out to the nearer one as a result of print bleeding.

Print missed: It occurs due to the fault of the print missed leads to the disagreement of the design with buyer swatch.

Design out: Design out is that fault of printed fabric in which design does not placed on fabric as result of any arease or wrinkle fabric.

Dust : Dust is a foreign substance that placed on fabric undesirably at the time of printing. As a result the design an that portion of fabric is disappeared after finishing.

Back Impression : Back impression is a fault which make the design shown at the back of the fabric due to the high viscosity of the paste.

CHAPTER 9

FINISHING SECTION

Finishing:

In textile manufacturing, finishing refers to the processes that convert the woven or knitted cloth into a usable material and more specifically to any process performed after dyeing the yarn or fabric to improve the look, performance, or "hand" (feel) of the finish textile or clothing. It's one of the most important operations in knit processing. Finishing is commonly divided into two categories, Chemical and Mechanical. In chemical finishing, water is used as the medium for applying the chemicals. Heat is used to drive off the water and to activate the chemicals. Mechanical finishing is considered a dry operation even though moisture and chemicals are often needed to successfully process the fabric.

Objectives of Finishing

- Improving the appearance, luster, whiteness etc.
- Improving the feel, which depends on the handle of the material & its softness, suppleness, fullness etc.
- Wearing qualities, non-soiling, antcrease, antishrink comfort etc.
- Special properties required for particular uses -water proofing flame proofing etc .
- Covering of the faults in the original cloth.
- Increasing the weight of the cloth .

Effects of Finishing

- Easy care .
- Crease recovery.
- Dimensional stability
- Good abrasion resistance
- Improved tear strength
- Good sew ability
- Soft or stiff handle
- Shine or luster

Knit fabrics require finishing process after dyeing. During dyeing all knit fabrics are dyed in tubular form. According to buyers requirement dyed fabrics are finished in either Tubular form or Open-width form.

Depending on which Finishing sections are separated into two sections – OPEN & TUBE section.

LAYOUT OF FINISHING SECTION

Open-finish Section:

Those fabrics which are to be cut in open form in garment section as per buyer requirement are finished in open form in this section.

The flow of process is as follow:

Tubular Fabric Finish Section:

Tubular fabrics are generally used for Ladies wear & Baby dress. In 4H group huge orders of tubular product are manufactured. The Machines or Finishing Sequence for Tube-Finishing are as follows:

HYDRO-EXTRACTOR-PADDER

Manufacturer : HUNG JYI, TAIWAN

No. of m/c : 2

Function:

1. To remove the excess water inherited by the fabric during Dyeing.
2. To clean any unnecessary dirt or hairs of fibers.
3. To soften the fabric if required by using softening agent.
4. Slight controlling of Dia of tube fabric by using 'Shaper'.

IMPORTANT PARTS & ZONES:

1. De-twister : Un-rove the roped form fabric after dyeing by twisting & turning.
2. J-Box : Overfeeding zone, which ensures tension-free movement of fabric.
3. Water & Softener bath : 1st bath is only water, 2nd one is for softener.
4. Padder: Two pairs of padding rollers set at the top of each bath. They squeeze the excess water from the fabric.
5. Ring & Ring Pulley: Works as a guide of fabric & maintain required Dia.
6. Technical Parameter:
7. 1. Fabric Passing Speed: Depends on count & GSM.
8. For Low GSM fabric - 60-65 m/min
9. For Medium - 55- 58 m/min
10. For High - 50-52 m/min
11. 2. Overfeed regions: J – box, Before Padder 1 & Padder 2
12. 3.Pressure in Padder: Padder 1: 4-5 bar; Padder 2: 3.5-4 bar

Important Parts & Zones:

DRYER

Manufacturer : HUNG JYI , TAIWAN.

Function:

1. To dry the wet fabric.
2. Control the shade & GSM slightly.

Main Parts:

- i. Feed unit; contains conveyor belt & number of rollers.
- ii. Two drying sections – i) upper level (3 chambers)
i. ii) Lower level (3chambers)
- iii. Heating system associated by GAS & Nozzles.

Technical Parameters:

- CHAMBER : 08
- TEMPARATURE : 130°C - 150°C
- Working width : 3000 mm
- Speed : 40-50 m/min
- Nozzle distance : 35-55 mm
- Power consumption : 140 kW

TUBE COMPACTOR

Manufacturer :USA

No. of m/c – 03

Function:

1. To control Dimensional stability of fabric.
2. Control GSM of fabric.
3. Make Shiny effect on fabric surface

Tube-tex Compactor (SOP)									
Color	Fabrics Types	Speed m/m	Temp.(°C) Cylinder	Steam	Pressure Blade	Pressure Shoe	Over Feed(%)	Dia(inches)S/J	
								shape Setting Dia	Reqd/Finish Dia
White	S/J	40	95	Full	3.0 to 7.0	8.0 to 12	100 to 108%	20.5	18.5
Black	S/J	40	95	Full	3.0 to 7.0	8.0 to 12	100 to 108%	22.5	20.5
White	1X1	40	95	Full	3.0 to 7.0	8.0 to 12	100 to 108%	24.5	22.5
Black	1X1	40	95	Full	3.0 to 7.0	8.0 to 12	100 to 108%	26.5	24.5
Others Col	S/J	40	95	Full	3.0 to 7.0	8.0 to 12	100 to 108%	28.5	26.5
Others Col	1X1	40	95	Full	3.0 to 7.0	8.0 to 12	100 to 108%		

SLITTING MACHINE

Manufacturer : HUNG JYI, TAIWAN.
 No. of machines : 2
 Manufacturer : BRUCKNER, GERMANY.
 No. of Machines : 1

Function:

- i. Slit-cut the tubular fabric through the needle mark.
- ii. Remove excess water.
- iii. Prepare the fabric for next operation.

Main Parts:

- Squeezer
- J-box
- Detwister
- Spreader

- Rotary cutting blade
- Auto Centering system
- Conveyor & Plaiter

Technical Parameters:

- Speed : Varies with type of fabric
- Overfeed : In feed zone, cutting zone, Conveyor belt (20-30%)
- Pressure : In De-twister zone-0.5 bar, in Padding – 4-5 bar

STENTER

Manufacturer	:	HUNG JYI, TAIWAN.
No. of machine	:	1
Manufacturer	:	BRUKNER, GERMANY.
No. of machine	:	2
Manufacturer	:	SUNSUPER, KOREA.
No. of machine	:	1

Function:

- Heat-set the synthetic fiber fabric.
- Controlling the width of fabric or maintain dimensional stability.
- Controlling the GSM of fabric.
- Skew ness & Bowing controlling of stripe fabric.
- Spirality & Twisting control.
- Fabric hand-feel modification-like-Softening or Hardening.
- Shade control.
- Gumming & Cutting.
- To dry the fabric.

Stenter m/c (full length view)

Stenter m/c (chain & clip system)

Important Zones & Parts:

Back Zone

- Guider
- Two Baths & Padder or Squeeze

- Auto centering
- Middle Zone
 - Over feed regions
 - Bianco or Mahlo arrangement.
 - Chain & clip system
 - Chambers (Contains blower, heater, recovery)
- Front Zone
 - Over feed zone
 - Plaiting
 - Static electricity remover.

Extra attachment:

- i) Mahlo attachment for bowing control.
- ii) Selvage gumming device
- iii) Selvage cutting device

Technical Parameters:

- Fuel used for heating : Gas (for Gas-Stenter)
Thermo-Oil (for Oil-Stenter)
- Working Width : 600-2600 mm
- Total Length : 138 ft

- No. of Chambers : 8
- Chamber length : 10 ft each
- No of Motors : 96
- Padder Pressure : Max. air Pressure – 10 bar (avg. 5-7)
Max. Steam Pressure – 0.7 bar
- Overfeed Ratio : Back Zone – 0-5
Master overfeed – 80% (in case of heat-set 15-20%)
Wheel overfeed – 3%
Feed overfeed – 3-5%
Take-up overfeed – 15-20%
- Temperature : Normal – 130-150°C
Heat-Set – 180-210°C
- Speed of Passing Fabric : Normally 35-40 m/min
Heat set 18-22 m/min
- Width Controlling : S/j +1-2 inches
Interlock/Rib - 1%
Lycra +8-10%
- Padder bath capacity : 250 lit
- Types of Softener used : White, Color, Silicon Softener

Production:

- Capacity: 5 tones/shift
- Actual production: 3.5-4.5 tones/shift

Heating Arrangement:

- For Gas Stenter: Rotamatic Burner
- For oil Stenter: Thermo-oil

Parameters used for different types of fabric:

BRUKNER

Fabric	Req. GSM	Finish GSM	R	F	B	Temperature	Speed m/min	Over feed
S/J	140	-	68"	71"	67"	140	14	80%

"	160	150/52	56"	64"	60"	150	20	80%
"	180	170/72	54"	56"	54.5"	110	12	60%
"	190	188/90	58"	61"	57"	110	15	80%
H/J	280	270/75	64"	67"	62"	110	7	80%
Loop back	280	255/60	74"	78"	75"	110	9	80%
Fleece	260	260/65	74"	80"	75"	110	9	80%
1x1 rib	240	224/26	72"	75"	74"	110	10	80%
Bolton stripe	330	340/45	62"	67"	65"	130	10	80%

M/C quantity	:	02
Brand	:	Brukner, Germany & HUNG JYI, TAIWAN.
Maxm line speed	:	60 m/min
Useable line speed	:	30 m/min Maxm dia :95 "
Workable dia	:	90"
Steam box temp.	:	80° C
Feed R/L temp.	:	105° C
Over feed (%)	:	upto 50 %
Shoe pressure	:	Max-18 Min-5
Sensor Position	:	-Shoe pressure (One shoe) -Retard Roller ratio -Pliater Ratio -Right-Left roller pressure

Function of the Machine:

1. To compact the fabric
2. To control the shrinkage
3. To maintain proper width and G.S.M

Heating system: Steam

Main parts of the machine:

1. Heating chamber
2. Blower (2, one at the entry chain zone for uncurling and another at the entry of compacting zone)
3. Synthetic blanket as a conveyor,
4. Folder
5. Exhaust fan

6. Unpinning cylinder (-40% +40%)
7. Belt cylinder (-40% +40%)
8. Uncurling device at entry of compacting zone.
9. Sensor
10. Brush roller

Additional attachment:

- i) Selvedge cutting
- ii) Selvedge safety
- iii) Pinning safety
- iv) Selvedge unrolling

COMPACTOR MACHINE

Manufacturer	:	HUNG JYI, TAIWAN.
No. of machines	:	2
Manufacturer	:	BRUCKNER, GERMANY.
No. of Machines	:	1
Manufacturer	:	SINTEC, ITALY.
No. of Machines	:	1

Function:

- i. To control Dimensional stability of fabric.
- ii. Control GSM of fabric.
- iii. To check shade.
- iv. It also reduces the yarn slippage.
- v. Increase smoothness of fabric.
- vi. Twisting control.

CHAPTER 10

QUALITY SECTION

Quality control in textiles is concerned with being certain a product meets performance standards and customer expectations.

Quality assurance is a way of preventing mistakes or defects in manufactured products & avoiding problems when delivering solutions or services to customers; which defines as, –part of quality management focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled||.

Objects of quality control

1. Research
2. Selection of raw material
3. process control
4. Process development
5. Product testing
6. Specification test

Types Of Quality Control:

- Online quality control
- Offline quality control

FLOWCHART OF QUALITY SECTION

LAYOUT OF QUALITY SECTION

Quality Assurance Procedure:

FOUR H GROUP assures the quality of their products in the following three steps:

1. In laboratory.
2. In dyeing section
3. In finishing section

The quality assurance procedures are described below:

In Laboratory

- Swatch card from buyer according to their requirement is received.
- Recipe prediction for sample dyeing using CCMS.
- Sample dyeing until matching with the swatch card. Acceptable color difference is less than 1.
- If matching is OK, then it is sent to the buyer for approval.

In Dyeing section:

- After approval form the buyer, sample dyeing is done in dyeing m/c, in dyeing shed & again matched with the approved sample.
- If result is OK, then balk production is commenced.
- During dyeing process, before the final acid wash, samples are taken and checked for accurate shade matching.
- After dyeing sample is collected & matching is done.
- Rubbing and wash fastness tests are carried out.

In finishing section:

- Correctly dyed, after treated & matched fabrics are allowed for finishing.
- By using a series of finishing machines correct width, softness & appearance are maintained according to requirements.
- Then sampling is done several times to test GSM, Shrinkage & fastness properties.
- Finally fabric is inspected & prepared for delivery.

In **4H GROUP** following flow diagram is followed-

FABRIC INSPECTION MACHINE

Physical test of fabric:

- Fabric weight
- Dimensional Changes in lengthwise
- Dimensional Changes in widthwise
- Seam Slippage
- Spirality test
- Pilling Resistance
- Softness test
- Hairiness test
- Brusting strength test

Chemical test of fabric:

- Fastness to rubbing
- Fastness to washing
- Fastness to perspiration
- Fastness to water
- Fastness to saliva

Besides these, for the best qualified production these Chemical Test should be performed-

- Fastness to light
- Fabric pH test
- Water hardness test

-Strength & Recovery test

-Wicking test

-Anti phenolic test

Problems Encountered in Dyeing

1. Uneven Dyeing

1. It can be caused due to rapid addition of dyes and chemicals. For this purpose the dosing of soda ash should be maintained properly.
2. Pressure difference.
3. Over loading in the m/c.
4. Yarn lot mixing.
5. Improper control of temperature.
6. Less amount of leveling agent.
7. Improper pretreatment.

2. Rope to Rope Uneven Shade

1. Improper rope length in each chamber.
2. Improper fabric flow speed in each nozzle.

3. Off Shade

1. Improper M: L ratio.
2. Lower amount of auxiliaries.
3. Improper mixing of dyestuffs.

- **Dye Spots**

This is most common fault caused by operator not correctly mixing and thoroughly dissolving dyestuffs in the right amount of water

- **Batch to Batch Shade Variation**

If any of parameters of dyeing are changed then it will produce problems in batch to batch consistency. In order to avoid this defect the following steps should be followed-

1. Maintain the same liquor ratio.
2. Check that the fabric has the same dye affinity.
3. Use the same standard program procedures for each batch.
4. Make sure that the operators add the right batch of chemicals at the same time & temperature in the process.
5. Check the water supply daily especially p^h , hardness & Na_2CO_3 content.

- **Crease Mark**

Crease marks are produced due to the lower concentration of anti-creasing agent and improper cooling rate (defective cooling gradient). This is encountered by increasing the concentration of anti-creasing agent and proper adjustment of cooling rate.

- **Running Marks**

Running marks are frequently related to the material construction and are caused by poor opening of the fabric rope.

1. Reducing the machine load and running at a slightly higher nozzle pressure, or using the next largest available nozzle size, may also help.
2. Either presetting or pre relaxation of the fabric before dyeing can avoid this problem
3. Running and crack marks can also be a result of incorrect process procedures. A higher fabric speed, combined with slower rates of rinse and cooling will often correct the problem.
4. Care should be taken to check that bath draining temperatures are not very high especially viscose blends are involved.
5. Shock cooling of static material will also cause crack mark

- **Intensive Foaming**

In case of intensive foaming, which is caused when, the pumps try to pump a mixture of air and water. This results in the loss of nozzle pressure & floating of flake. If the foaming is severe it is better to drop the bath & restart the process, after adding an anti-foaming agent to the new bath.

- **Patchy Dyeing**

It is caused, if dye solution is not correct and also scouring is improper.

- **Miscellaneous Problems**

Batch to batch processing may vary due to the improper calculation of dyes and chemicals and improper strength of salt soda and H₂O₂ etc. Beside hardness of water and caustic may lead to an improper shade.

<i>Defect</i>	<i>Image</i>
<i>Holes</i>	
<i>Barrie</i>	
<i>Broken needle</i>	
<i>Dropped stitch</i>	
<i>Fly</i>	
<i>Oily yarns</i>	

<i>Knots</i>	
<i>Thick yarn</i>	
<i>Thin yarn</i>	

Finished fabric Inspection :

The final product should pass against the norms given by the buyer. The following tests are done-

- Shade check
- Gsm test
- Width or diameter test
- Shrinkage test
- Crocking test
- Pilling resistance test
- Color fastness to test
- Color fastness to perspiration
- Dimensional stability

For final inspection , Inspection table & Inspection m/c is used .

The 4-point system is given below-

Size of Defect	Penalty point
Less than 3 inches	1
3-6 inches	2
More than 6- 9 inch	3
More than 9 inch	4

Size of holes & opennings-

1 inch or less	2
More than 1 inch	4

Some general rules of the inspection are-

1. Not 1 metre of cloth is penalized more than 4 points.
2. Cloth is inspected on face side only unless specified.

If the total defect parts per 100 yards of fabric are 40 or more the fabric will be rejected. But it may be changed according to buyer's requirements

Shade check :

The shade achieved is to be checked several times while in process & at finished state to ensure the customers demand under recommended light source .Generally the shade is checked at the following stage

- After dyeing
- After drying
- After trial for finishing
- After finishing

During dyeing period in QC there is a shade matching sequence:

For this the following equipments are used :

1.Verivide light box

Manufacturer: Cundy building , frog island Origin : England

Light Source :

D-65 (artificial day light)

TL-84 (Shop light)

F (florescent light)

UV (Ultraviolet Blue light)

Procedure of GSM measurement by GSM cutter :

1. Cut the fabric with the G.S.M cutter.

2. Weight the fabric with the electric balance .

3. The cut sample is 100 sq.cm. The weight of the cut sample is multiplied by 100.

4. The result is the G.S.M of that particular fabric .

Suppose ,

The weight of the fabric is 2.51 gm. That means the G.S.M of the fabric is 251 gm.

Specification of GSM cutter :

Name: G.S.M CUTTER

Manufacturer: James H.Heal & Company limited.

Origin : England.

CHAPTER 11

UTILITY

Available utilities:

The following utility facilities are available:

- Water
- Steam
- Electricity
- Gas
- Compressed air
- Covered van for transformation

Sources of utilities:

- Water - Natural water by own supply
- Steam - Own supply from boiler
- Electricity - Generator & PDB
- Compressed air - Own supply air compressor

SL.	Name of Machine	Capacity	Brand	Origin	Qty
01	Steam Boiler	10 Ton	Loos	Germany	02
02	Gas Generator	1030 KW	CAT	USA	03
03	Air Compressor	10 Bar	Quincy	USA	05
04	Diesel Generator	160 KVA		Italy	01
05	Diesel Generator	400 KVA		Italy	01
06	Auto Condensate & Flash steam recovery	10000 kg/hr	BD	Bangladesh	01
07	Hot Water Module	100 m ³ /h	BD	Bangladesh	01
08	Thermo oil Boiler	3 Ton	Inplan	Germany	01

09	R.O Plant	20 m ³ /h		India	01
10	Booster Pump	100 m ³ /h	KSB	India	01
11	WTP	100 m ³ /h	Ion exchange	India	02
12	ETP	100 m ³ /h	Ion exchange	India	01

LAYOUT OF 4H UTILITY

In FOUR H Dyeing , Printing & Finishing has own generator section or power house section. Total 03 number of modern gas & desile generators are 24hours running for producing electricity to run the industrial production properly.

Picture: GAS GENERATOR

The Generator Machine Specification & details is given in below:

BRAND NAME	CATERPILLAR ENGINEER (CAT)
MODEL	3
MACHINE NAME	GAS
TOTAL NO.	02
CAPACITY	1.6 Mw PER GENERATOR
COUNTRY ORIGIN	USA
YEAR	2017
GAS PRESSURE	1.5 TO 10 PSI
VOLTAGE	400
FREQUENCE	50

BOILER

In Four H dyeing & Printing floor is supported by individual boiler. The specification of the boiler is given below:

Type: smoke tube package boiler

Model: dl-z 15000

Actual evaporation: 15000 kg/hr

Design pressure: 1 mpa

Heat efficiency: 90%

Fuel consumption: 1095 nm²/hr,
r, kg/hr (LNG, light oil)

Heating surface: 276 m²

Burner:

Model: dlrc-1000

Fuel: LNG

Supply gas pressure: 39.2 to 88.2

Using: 13.7 to 29.4

Gas consumption: 136 to 952 nm

FD fan:

Type: turbo

Capacity: 270 m³/min

Power: 45 kw

Rpm: 2935

Safety valve:

Normal size: 65 A, 65A

Setting pressure: 1 mpa

Capacity: 17040 kg/hr.

LOOS BOILER

CHAPTER 12

WATER TREATMENT PLANT

Ion exchange is an effective, versatile means of conditioning boiler feed water. The term –ion exchange|| describes the process: as water flows through a bed of ion exchange material, undesirable ions are removed and replaced with less objectionable ones. For example, in softening processes, calcium and magnesium ions (hardness) are exchanged for sodium ions. In dealkalization, the ions contributing to alkalinity (carbonate, bicarbonate-ate, etc.) are removed and replaced with chloride ions. Other dealkalization processes utilizing weak acid cation resin or strong acid cation resin in a split stream process, exchange cations with hydrogen. This forms carbonic acid which can be removed in ad carbonator tower. Demineralization is simply replacing all cations with hydrogen ions (H^+) and all anions with hydroxide ions (OH^-). Ion exchange materials are like storage batteries; they must be recharged (regenerated) periodically to restore their exchange capacity. With proper design and operation, ion exchange processes are capable of removing selected ions almost completely (in some cases to a fraction of a part per million).

ION EXCHANGE MATERIALS

Ion exchange processes are versatile specific types of ions can be removed from water depending on the choice of exchange material and regenerant used.

Development

Slightly more than 100 years ago, two English agricultural chemists, H. S. Thompson and J. Thomas Way, noted that certain soils had a greater ability than others to absorb ammonia from fertilizers. They found that complex silicates in the soil performed an ion exchange function. They were able to prepare materials of this type in the laboratory from solutions of sodium aluminate and sodium silicate. In 1906, Robert Gans used materials of this type for softening water. The early materials used were slow in regenerating and lacked physical stability. These first synthetic, inorganic exchangers were called zeolites. Today, zeolites are almost totally replaced by synthetic ion exchange materials.

Cation exchangers

There has been constant improvement in ion exchange materials since the first use of natural and synthetic inorganic products. Sulfonated coal, styrene-base resins, phenolic resins and acrylic resins are some that have been developed. Exchange capacities were greatly increased with the development of the styrene-base exchangers. These resins are manufactured in spherical, stress and strain-free form to resist physical degradation. They are stable at temperatures as high as 300°F and are applicable over a wide pH range. More dense resins, those having greater degrees of copolymer cross-linking, were specially developed for heavy duty industrial applications. These products are more resistant to degradation by oxidizing agents such as chlorine, and withstand physical stresses that fracture lighter duty materials. Weakly acidic cation exchange resins contain carboxylic and phenolic groups. They remove alkalinity by exchanging their hydrogen ions for the cations associated with the bicarbonate ion (calcium, magnesium, and sodium bicarbonates). Being weakly acidic, they will not affect the cations associated with the anions of strong acids (chlorides or sulfates). Because of almost 100% utilization of the regenerant acid, chemical operating costs will be at a minimum, and there will be little excess acid to produce objectionable waste effluents.

Anion exchangers

Anion exchange materials are classified as either weak base or strong base depending on the type of exchange group. Weak base resins act as acid absorbers, efficiently removing strong acids such as sulfuric and hydrochloric. However, they will not remove carbon dioxide or silica. They are used in systems where strong acids predominate, where silica reduction is not required, and where carbon dioxide is removed in degasifiers. Preceding strong base units in dematerializing processes, weak base resins give more economical removal of sulfates and chlorides.

These are two general classes of strong base anion exchangers, Types I and II, denoting differences in chemical nature. Both remove silica and carbon dioxide as well as other anions. Type I is more effective in removing silica, and is used when the combined silica and carbon dioxide content of the water contacting the exchanger is more than 25% of the total anions. When there is contamination of the water with organic matter, a more porous form of Type I resin is recommended. The Type II anion material is used in treating waters where the combined carbon dioxide and silica content is less than 25% of the total anions. This is often the case when carbon dioxide is taken out in a degasifier ahead of the anion exchanger unit

Physical Characteristics of Resin

Anion and cation resins can be obtained in several different physical forms. They can be obtained with different ions located on the exchange site. This has importance in applications such as mixed beds where minimal leakage rates are required even from a newly installed bed. Particle size can also be specified. Uniform particle sized (UPS) resins are now available where all beads fit into a very close particle size range. For practical purposes, all of the beads are the same size. Beds of UPS resins have some unique operating characteristics which offer advantages when they are used in mixed bed, layered bed, and packed bed applications. Macro porous resins are highly porous which give them advantages when used in processes that have high fouling potential.

ION EXCHANGE PROCESSES

Ion exchange processes fall into several categories: softening (including removal of iron and manganese), dealkalization, and demineralization.

Equipment operation

Ion exchange material is housed in specially constructed tanks where it forms a bed, usually 30–60 inches deep. In some cases, it is supported by another bed of graded gravel or anthracite filter media. In other cases, some special methods of support, without gravel or anthracite, are used. During normal operation, water enters the top of the tank through a pipe, which distributes it over the surface of the exchanger bed. The treated water is drawn off by collector piping at the bottom. Several newer designs for ion exchange are now coming into common use. These are becoming popular because of their advantages of higher operating efficiencies and lower leakage rates. In countercurrent regeneration procedures, the regenerant flow is opposite in direction to the service water flow. Therefore, the resin located in the bed where the finished water leaves the vessel, is the most highly regenerated. This results in lower leakage rates and slightly higher operating capacities at equal regenerant dosages to concurrent operated vessels. However, countercurrent vessels are more sensitive to operating problems. The bed must be immobilized during the regeneration process and the influent water must be very low in suspended solids.

Figure 2 illustrates what happens in the two regeneration modes at exhaustion and after regeneration. Packed bed systems essentially fill the vessel with resin. The

systems are countercurrent in design and offer the low leakage rate advantage. However, packed beds also offer the advantage of reduced waste generation. Since there is no space for proper backwash, packed bed systems usually are built with external backwash tanks which allow the resin to be backwashed after it is sluiced out of the operating vessel. All countercurrent ion exchange systems require feed water that is very low in suspended solids. Regeneration of the exchange material involves three steps: backwash, introduction of the regeneration chemicals, and rinse. Figure shows valve arrangements on a salt regenerated unit. Backwash is simply a reversal of the normal flow to wash out any suspended matter in the bed and to —fluff the bed, to break up packed areas. This is done just before the unit is regenerated. During regeneration, chemicals are introduced at the top surface of the bed and removed through the bottom outlet. The rinse washes out the last traces of regenerant chemical

When regeneration is ineffective, the bed is usually fouled with suspended matter. This emphasizes the importance of proper backwash procedures. During backwash, the cation exchanger bed should expand at least 50%, while the anion exchanger bed should expand at least 75%. How much the bed expands depends on the backwash water temperature, backwash rate and density of the ion exchange. The capacity of ion exchange material varies according to the amount and concentration of regenerating chemical used and the time the chemical contacts the exchanger. Table 3 shows this variation in capacity with regenerant dosages. Selecting the optimum dosage level depends mainly on the quality of finished water required, considering both economic and operating factors.

PICTURE OF WTP

Fig: Water Treatment Plant

CHAPTER 13

EFFLUENT TREATMENT PLANT

Effluent treatment plant used to remove the color, chemicals that present in the water comes from the dyeing house. Dye house water contains several chemicals in the different stages of the processing as follows-

The major sources of liquid discharge are:

- Scouring.
- Bleaching.
- Dyeing.
- Washing

After bleaching the water contains

- Dilute hypochlorite solution.
- H₂O₂

Besides dye used (Reactive, Disperse) are also present in the water

Other processes that are present in the water include:

- Detergent
- Soda ash
- Caustic soda.
- Stabilizer
- Acetic acid.

Type

There are mainly three types of ETP. They are:

1. Biological ETP
2. Physio-Chemical ETP
3. Physio-Chemical & Biological ETP

LAYOUT OF ETP

FOUR H DYEING & PRINTING LTD.
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কেমিক্যাল মিশ্রণ এবং ব্যবহার পদ্ধতি

Lime (CaO) 5% — ১০০০ লিটার পানির মধ্যে ৫০ কেজি।
 FeSo₄ 5% — ১০০০ লিটার পানির মধ্যে ৫০ কেজি।
 Polyelectrolyte 1% — ১০০০ লিটার পানির মধ্যে ১ কেজি।
 (Hcl) Acid 11% — ১০০০ লিটার পানির মধ্যে ১১০ কেজি। (পানির pH এর উপর নির্ভরশীল)
 Urea/DAP 7.5% — ১০০০ লিটার পানির মধ্যে ৭৫ কেজি।
 Sodium Hypo Chlorite (NaOCL) 10% — ১০০০ লিটার পানির মধ্যে ১০০ কেজি।

প্রতিটি ট্যাঙ্কে কেমিক্যালের ব্যবহার ও এর কাজ :

Bar Chamber:
 বার চেম্বার প্রাথমিক চিকিৎকার হিসেবে কাজ করে, বর্জ্য পানির মাঝে 'পুস্ট', সোডিয়াম, বোরাক্স, পলিভিন ইত্যাদি মাঝে ইকোলোজিক্যাল ট্যাঙ্কে রূপান্তর করতে বা পাঠবে, সেজন্য বার চেম্বার স্থাপন করা হয়।

Equalization Tank:
 ইকোলোজিক্যাল ট্যাঙ্কে কারখানার সকল জলসমৃদ্ধ জমা হয়, এখানে এরপর প্রকারান্তরে করা হয়, এরপর প্রত্যেকের কাজ হয়ে ট্রাজ কে পানির মাঝে মিশ্রিত করা ও তাৎক্ষণিকভাবে জমাট বাঁধতে পা দেওয়া হয়।

Flocculation Tank:
 এই ট্যাঙ্কে Equalization tank হইতে পাঠানোর মাধ্যমে উচ্চলব্ধ পানির pH দেখা দেয়। পানির pH এর মাল অনুযায়ী কেমিক্যালের কম বেশী দেওয়া হয়। এই ট্যাঙ্কে Lime, FeSo₄ এবং polyelectrolyte দেওয়া হয়। Lime ও FeSo₄ এর কাজ হচ্ছে অম্লীয় এবং কেমিক্যাল মুক্ত পানিকে ছোট ছোট sludge এর পানিকে করা করে Polyelectrolyte এর কাজ হচ্ছে ছোট ছোট sludge এর পানিকে বড় sludge এর পানিকে করা।

Lamella Clarifier: এই ট্যাঙ্কে Tube Media এর কাজ হচ্ছে অম্লীয়কে উপরে উঠতে না দেওয়া, এখানে Tube Media স্থাপন হিসেবে ব্যবহার করা হয়।

pH Correction Tank: এই ট্যাঙ্কে পানির pH এর মাল ঠিক রাখা হয়। পানির pH ঠিক রাখার জন্য হাইড্রোক্লোরিক এসিড (HCl Acid) ব্যবহার করা হয়, হাইড্রোক্লোরিক এসিড (HCl Acid) ব্যবহারের দিকে করে পানির pH এর উপর। যদি বর্জ্য পানির pH বেশী হয় তাহলে হাইড্রোক্লোরিক এসিডের পরিমাণ বাড়ানো হয়।

Biological Tank: এই ট্যাঙ্কে বোরাক্স এবং পলিভিন ইত্যাদি মিশ্রিত করা হয়, বায়োলেজিক্যাল ট্যাঙ্কে বায়োলেজিক্যাল মিশ্রিত করা হয়, এখানে বায়োলেজিক্যালের কাজ হচ্ছে পানির মাঝে মিশ্রিত করা করে এবং B.O.D ও C.O.D এর মাল এই ট্যাঙ্কে বায়োলেজিক্যালের মাধ্যমে হিসেবে Nutrient - (Urea) ব্যবহার করা হয়।

Chlorination Tank: এই ট্যাঙ্কে Sodium Hypo Chloride (NaOCL) কেমিক্যালের বায়োলেজিক্যালের মাধ্যমে করা হয়, কেমিক্যালের বায়োলেজিক্যালের (NaOCL) এর কাজ হচ্ছে বায়োলেজিক্যাল ট্যাঙ্কে হইতে পানির মাঝে মাল বায়োলেজিক্যালের কাজ করে পানিকে ঠিকঠাক মুক্ত করা।

Sludge Sump:
 এই ট্যাঙ্কে Flocculation tank, Lamella Clarifier Biological tank এর সব মাল বা Sludge জমা করা হয়।

Centrifuge Pump:
 Sludge Sump এর মাল (Sludge) সেপারেশন পানির মাঝে করা হয় এবং মাল পানি সেপারেশন করা হয় এবং মাল মাল Hydro Extractor এর মাধ্যমে সেপারেশন করা হয়, এবং পানি সেপারেশন করা করে জমা রাখা হয়।

Process Description of ETP

1. Screening: Effluent coming from fabric processing unit may contain chemical lump, solid particles, rags and other big particles which are totally removing in screening by two automatic rotary screens.

Fig: Screening

2. Homogenization Feeding (Size: Width-4.2m, Length-6.8m, Useful Height-2.0m): All the screened water are being collected in homogenization feeding tank from where all the effluent are being transferred to homogenization tank by three submersible feed pumps which are automatically controlled by PLC.

3. Homogenization Tank (Size: Width-24m, Length-31.7m, Useful Height-6m, Volume-4565m³): All the effluents enter into this tank are homogenizing by two automatically controlled hydrodynamic cavitations pump. Here all effluent are mixing properly, reduce temperature, decrease the COD.

Fig: Homogenization Tank

4. Biological Feeding (Size: Width-2.3m, Length-3m, Useful Height-6.0m): Effluent from homogenization tank is feed to biological tank through biological feeding where effluent pH is maintained by adding acid (sulphuric/hydrochloric) by automatic dosing pump. Nutrients (phosphoric acid & acetic acid) are also added here for growing micro-organism.

5. Biological De-nitrification (Size Tank-A: Width-A-13.53m, Width-B-12.54m, Length-10.4m, Useful Height-7.4m. Useful Volume-1000m³; Tank-B: Width-13m, Length-10.4, Useful Height-7.4m, Useful Volume-1000m³): The flow that comes from the homogenization phase it mixed with the activated sludge which deperate the waste water. It helps to remove nitric nitrogen created in the oxidation tank. It permits to create anoxic condition for the nitrates to gaseous nitrogen.

6. Biological Tank (Size: Width-A-29.85m, Width-B-27.05m, Length-29.7m, Useful Height-7.1m, Useful Volume-6000m³): The effluents fall by gravity from the de-nitrification tank to the biological tank. Here the pollutants are oxidized by the activated sludge. Here the nitrogenous substances are turned into nitrates by biomass. Air is supplied in this tank by air blowers.

Fig: Biological Tank

7. Clarifier (Size: Side-A-10.3m, Side-B-10.1, Surface-10m², Approx Volume-685m³): The effluent coming from the biological tank allows the sludge to settle down. For proper quick settling, a lamellar settler is being used. The settled sludge is then re-circulating to the de-nitrification tank by pump.

From the clarifier the overflow water is draining out by gravitational force as exit water.

8. Sludge Thickener: If the activated sludge quantity becomes very high, then from the clarifier sludge transfer to the sludge thickener. From here it sends to the sludge de-watering section for drying and bagging.

ETP LAYOUT

CHAPTER 15

CONCLUSION

I am very glad that I've completed my industrial training successfully by the grace of Almighty. Textile education is based on industrial ground. Theoretical background is not sufficient. Hence industrial training plays an important role to make a technologist technically sound. Industrial training provides the opportunity to gather practical knowledge. For every person who is a fresher in the field of textile, industrial training works like learning route. It gives me the opportunity to move liberally in every section of the industry to learn the industrial work and follow the process sequence virtually.

4H GROUP is one of the best factories in the textile field of Bangladesh. It is a utopia for the professional aspirants in textile sector. It is well equipped and the working environment is excellent. The relation between top management to bottom level is so nice. I am lucky to get the opportunity of having training in this mill. The factory runs by a number of efficient textile engineers, skilled technical & non-technical persons. All the textile engineers, technical & non-technical persons are very sincere, co-operative and helpful.

I feel very privileged to get the opportunity to complete my internship program at 4HGROUP. I wish best of luck for this factory and all its personnel.

THANK YOU....

AT THE END:

It's an honor for me that I have got an opportunity of having training in this mill. During the training period I received co-operation & association from the authority full and found all man, machines & materials on appreciable working condition. All stuff & officers are very sincere & devoted their duties to achieve their goal.

Special thanks & gratefulness to those whom I am grateful....

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ENGR. SHOHEL (Asst. EXECUTIVE, PRINTING)

All other personnel who helped me lot to learn so many things.

The end
